

D1.2 Report on directed evolution of proteins

Name of project: Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
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Author(s):	Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc. Mgr. Mária Tomková, PhD. RNDr. Veronika Dzurillová RNDr. Martin Berta
Reviewer:	Prof. Dr. Andreas Plückthun
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APPROVALS

Task leader: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.
 WP leaders: Prof. Dr. Andreas Plückthun,
 Prof. Dr. Matthias Rief,
 Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.
 Project coordinator: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BCA assay	bicinchoninic acid assay
BSA	bovine serum albumin
CDR	complementarity determining regions
CeVICA	cell-free nanobody engineering platform
CTLA4	cytotoxic T lymphocyte-associated protein 4
DMSO	dimethyl sulfoxide
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
DTT	dithiothreitol
<i>E.coli</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
ELISA	enzyme-linked immuno sorbent assay
EPO	erythropoietin
FACS	Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting
G-CSF	Granulocyte colony-stimulating factor
GdnHCl	guanidine hydrochloride
GPCR	G-protein coupled receptor
HIC	hydrophobic interaction chromatography
HLD	haloalkane dehalogenase
IgG	immunoglobulin
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
PLG	plasminogen
PLM	plasmin
RAGE	receptor for advanced glycation end products
RBD	receptor-binding domain
RBS	ribosome binding site
RD	ribosome display
SAK	staphylokinase
<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>
SEC	size exclusion chromatography
StEP	staggered extension process
WT	wild-type
YSD	yeast surface display

PURPOSE OF THE REPORT

The summarizing expert report on a reached stage of directed evolution methods, ribosome and yeast displays at UPJS. Besides the interim role as seed for the protein evolution methods expertise, this report will be a crucial starting point for subsequent, extremely competitive EU grant proposals submitted with the current Partners and additional participants.

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1. PROTEIN EVOLUTION METHODS

The concept of laboratory-directed protein evolution is not new. Systematic approaches to directed evolution of proteins have been documented since the 1970s [Campbell et al. 1973, Hall & Hartl 1974]. One early example is the evolution of the EbgA protein from *Escherichia coli*, an enzyme having almost no β -galactosidase activity. Through intensive selection of a LacZ⁻ deletion strain of *E. coli* for growth on lactose as a sole carbon source, the wild-type EbgA was “evolved” as a β -galactosidase sufficient to replace the lacZ gene function [Campbell et al. 1973]. Perhaps surprisingly, the evolution of new functions of an enzyme can require few mutations, as was the case for the EbgA protein. EbgA enzyme variants with newly acquired hydrolytic activities toward a variety of β -galactoside sugars contain only one to three mutations [Hall 1981, 2002, 2003]. The ability to recruit new protein functions arised from the considerable substrate ambiguity of many proteins [Jensen 1976]. The substrate ambiguity of a protein can be interpreted as the evolutionary potential that allows a protein to acquire new specificities through mutation or to regain function via mutations that differ from the original protein sequence. All organisms have evolutionarily exploited this substrate ambiguity. When exploited in a laboratory under controlled mutagenesis and selection, it enables a protein to “evolve” in desired directions.

Directed protein evolution is a general term used to describe various techniques for generation of protein mutants (variants) and selection of desirable functions. Over the last three decades, directed protein evolution has emerged as a powerful technology platform in protein engineering. This technology has been advanced considerably by the availability of molecular biology tools and emerging high-throughput screening technologies. These methodologies have simplified the experimental processes and facilitated the identification of mutants with even small improvements in desired function. Advanced recombinant DNA technologies have allowed the transfer of single structural genes or genes for an entire pathway to a suitable surrogate host for rapid propagation and/or high-level protein production. Furthermore, it is now possible to control the rate of mutagenesis in widely applied methods such as error-prone PCR and to modify proteins by systematic insertions or deletions. In addition, site-directed, site-saturation mutagenesis and synthetic

oligonucleotides can be used to expand the localized amino acid diversity. While functional complementation of mutant strains is still an excellent choice when possible, the development of sensitive instrumentation and the ability to miniaturize many chemical or biological assays allow the screening of large numbers of samples for selection of desired functions. The ability to rapidly obtain DNA sequence information for gene variants not only provides insight into protein sequence-function relationship but also enhances our ability to select the strategy best suited for the evolution of a particular protein. Thus, directed protein evolution has been expanded from the original *in vivo* approach (e.g., the evolution of EbgA) to include *in vitro* exploration.

One of the most effective strategies in directed protein evolution is to gradually accumulate mutations, either sequentially or by recombination, while applying selective pressure. This is typically achieved by the generation of libraries of mutants followed by efficient screening of these libraries for targeted functions and subsequent repetition of the process using improved mutants from the previous screening. Many formats of directed protein evolution have been, and continue to be, developed [Yuan et al. 2005].

1.1. Strategies for directed evolution in protein design

One of the primary goals of protein design is to generate proteins with new or improved properties. In addition to deepening our understanding of the design processes used in nature, the ability to confer a desired activity on a protein or enzyme has considerable practical application in the chemical, agricultural, and pharmaceutical industries. Two strategies are currently being employed towards this goal. The first is directed evolution, in which libraries of variants are searched experimentally for clones possessing the desired properties. The second is rational design, in which proteins are modified based on an understanding of the structural and mechanistic consequences of a particular change or set of changes. While the power of directed evolution is now widely appreciated, our present knowledge of structure-function relationships in proteins is still insufficient to make rational design a robust approach.

Evolution has generated the great diversity of proteins with all different features required for the processes of life primarily by using the 20 amino acids available in nature. Despite all our efforts to fully understand the nature of proteins, we are still far from being able to create completely new proteins with desired structure and function merely by rational design. By utilizing state-of-the-art in vitro evolution technology it is possible to generate protein variants with new features. However, it is a challenge to predict what combination of changes in the different amino acid residues that is needed to design a protein with novel functionality but with retained structure. The desired function could for example be improved stability or solubility, or modified substrate specificity or improved properties of an enzyme. Hereinafter the focus in this report will be on the generation of proteins with novel binding specificity, i.e. affinity proteins. When developing affinity proteins with new binding specificities, proteins can be selected for the capability to bind to a target molecule. There are a variety of different strategies, commonly termed protein selection systems, for isolating proteins with new target affinity from a combinatorial protein library.

Since sequencing of proteins is difficult, all successful affinity protein selection systems are all based on linkage between the genotype and phenotype of the affinity protein. This enables easy identification and amplifications of the selected polypeptides via the nucleic acids, being

Figure 1. Schematic of molecular evolution of proteins. First, gene encoding the protein of interest is subjected to mutagenesis to generate a gene library. Subsequently, proteins are expressed from the gene and evaluated for their function. Then, proteins with the desired properties are selected. In this step, while the selection is carried out based on the properties of proteins, the genes encoding them should be selected simultaneously, which requires physical linkage between genotype and phenotype [Matsuura & Yomo 2006].

DNA or RNA. The selection procedure can be summarized in the steps: diversification, selection and amplification (Figure 1). This includes construction of a protein or peptide library, screening for binding to a defined target molecule, amplification of selected molecules and identification of binding clones. The selection process is typically repeated a number of times, i.e. in cycles, to enrich molecules with desired binding properties. After selection and identification, the selected novel protein is typically recombinantly produced and characterized in more detail. The need for different selection systems, all with their advantages and limitations, are due to a number of factors, e.g. availability and inherent properties of the target protein, and therefore a number of different selection methods has evolved. The success of a selection strategy depends to high extent on the diversity and quality of the constructed library. However, methods for construction of affinity protein libraries will not be discussed in detail in this review. The different selection systems, described below, can

		Cellular Requirement				DNA / RNA template		
		Phage Display	Yeast Display	Bacterial (<i>E. coli</i>) Display	Mammalian Cell Display	<i>In vitro</i> compartmentalisation	Ribosome display	mRNA Display
Genotype-phenotype Linkage								
		Genetic fusion to Protein III, expressed on the surface of M13 phage	Display on yeast cell surface via fusion with cell-surface anchor proteins (e.g. agglutinin protein Aga2p)	Protein anchored on inner periplasmic membrane via the Tat transport system & signal peptide ssTorA. Outer membrane is lysed	Episomal vectors transfected into mammalian cells (e.g. HEKs) expressing IgGs on cell surface	Physical encapsulation of DNA/RNA template with protein expressed in artificial cells (e.g. emulsion droplets)	mRNA and translated protein linked via a ribosome stalled in translation	Covalent attachment of nascent peptide chain to mRNA via a 3' puromycin
Typical Display Size		$\sim 10^8 - 10^{10}$	$\sim 10^7 - 10^9$	$\sim 10^9$	$\sim 10^7$	$\sim 10^8$	$\sim 10^{12} - 10^{13}$	$\sim 10^{12} - 10^{13}$
Features and Considerations		Robust and well-established technology; phage stable and tolerant to selections under harsh conditions	Selection of binders via fluorescence activated sorting (FACS) allows for multi-parameter screening (e.g. binding & expression)	Displayed proteins are generally well-folded due to quality control mechanism of Tat pathway. Other formats (e.g. with chaperones) available	Facile Induction of somatic hypermutation via AID; simultaneous display and secretion of IgGs, no reformatting requirements	Multiple formats available; e.g. microbead, DNA, SNAP display etc. <i>In vitro</i> transcription-translation; no selection bias	Large display capacity to accommodate complex library builds, cell-independent and no selection bias, directed evolution	Stable covalent linkage enabling selections under wide range of conditions, large library size and no selection bias
		Low display capacity. Selection bias favoring selection of high-expressing clones (as opposed to strong binders)	Low transformation efficiency leading to limited library size	Low transformation efficiency. Lysis requirement lowers <i>E. coli</i> stability which can restrict selection conditions and efficiency	Practical limitations in cell handling and transfection densities leading to small display size	Library size must be kept low to ensure spatial segregation of individual clones	Possible affinity ceiling; low-affinity variants may not be selected	Potential difficulties in displaying large proteins and membrane proteins

Figure 2. Comparison of different display technologies with different strengths and limitations; features which may guide the design of an effective affinity maturation strategy [Chan & Groves 2021].

be divided into two different categories: cell-dependent display systems (cellular requirement) and cell-free display systems (DNA/RNA template) (Figure 2).

1.2. Applications of directed evolution

Directed evolution is increasingly used in academic and industrial laboratories to improve protein stability and enhance the activity or overall performance of enzymes and organisms or to alter enzyme substrate specificity and to design new activities. Together with novel techniques for large-scale screening, directed evolution enables the selection of redesigned molecules without the necessity for detailed structural and mechanistic information. In the past years we have seen broad applications of directed evolution in research and product developments of recombinant DNA technologies, biocatalysts, metabolic pathway engineering, pharmaceuticals, and important agricultural traits. Regardless of the research discipline, some common themes or parameters can be observed in the application of directed evolution. For example, directed evolution increasingly appears to be the tool of choice for studying the evolution of and relationship between protein structure and function and for interpretation of the evolutionary significance of biomolecular systems [Yuan et al. 2005]. It is also a popular tool for accelerated adaptation of protein functions (e.g., stability, specificity, or affinity) in extreme conditions such as unusual temperatures and organic solvents [Grönwall & Ståhl 2009, Chan & Groves 2021, Piszkin & Bowman 2021, Pongsupasa et al. 2022], as well as for improvement of recombinant protein biosynthesis [Schütz et al. 2016]. Directed evolution has also given rise to altered specificities and activities of enzymes [Yu et al. 2022], enhanced intramolecular interactions, modified protein-protein interaction, and altered metabolic pathways.

2. RIBOSOME DISPLAY

Biological evolution uses mutations as its basic working approach. Mutations occur in DNA molecules through various mechanisms. Some mutations are relatively 'silent' and as such their effects are less appreciated, whereas others have a more prominent impact on the biological function of proteins/enzymes. Mutations leading to amino-acid substitutions usually affect protein biophysical properties, such as stability, folding kinetics, interactions, functional dynamics and others. Therefore, in the nature, only mutations maintaining functional properties of the protein persist. The basic requirement for protein function is proper folding into a unique and stable structure, thus, protein sequence evolution is constrained by the biophysics of folding, causing interdependence between interacting sites in the sequence. Moreover, protein biological function depends also on the ability to bind the target ligands [Grahnen et al. 2011, Sikosek et al 2014]. Protein stability and binding are properties that can be engineered also in vitro by directed evolution. Similar to natural selection, directed evolution is based on the fact that genetic diversity leads to phenotypic diversity. It takes advantage of random mutagenesis to generate a broad set of protein variants, of protein production in the host cells, and of the recovery and amplification of clones based on a link between genotype and phenotype. The library design, evolutionary landscape, phenotypic target, and screening system are all among the critical components of a successful directed evolution. Display techniques provide a robust platform for the directed evolution of protein variants using high-throughput in vitro screening method. One of them, ribosome display, has developed into a robust technology used in academia and industry alike, and it has made the cell-free Darwinian evolution of proteins over multiple generations a reality.

Ribosome display (Figure 3) was first developed by Hanes and Plückthun [Hanes and Plückthun 1997] for the selection of folded proteins. An inherent prominent advantage of ribosome display is that it permits Darwinian protein evolution to occur in vitro via alternating cycles of mutagenesis and selection. In this innovative technology, genes (genotype) linked to the displayed protein variants (phenotype) can be easily traced. The physical link between genotype and phenotype is accomplished by a mRNA–ribosome–protein complex that is used

Figure 3. Overview of the ribosome display selection round. (1-3) A DNA library in the form of a PCR product is ligated into the vector specially designed for RD (pRDV). DNA library is genetically fused to a sequence providing a promoter and translation initiation region and *tolA* spacer sequence. (4) Final ribosome display constructs are obtained by PCR amplification of the library inserts and flanking regions from the ligated plasmid. (5) In vitro transcription of this PCR product yields mRNA that is used for in vitro translation. (6) During translation, mRNA-ribosome-protein ternary complex is created, and the ribosome does not release the properly folded protein because it does not have a stop codon. (7) The mRNA-ribosome-protein ternary complexes are used for affinity selection on an immobilized antigen. (8) After washing, mRNA of bound ternary complex is (9) eluted and purified, (10) reverse transcribed and amplified by PCR. Such PCR products of selected protein variants are used as a starting point for further rounds of ribosome display.

for selection (Figure 1, step 7). A construct designed for use with *E. coli* extracts, typically consists of a T7 promoter that allows mRNA synthesis, followed by a ribosome binding site (RBS) that can base-pair with ribosomal RNA thus recruiting the ribosome to the downstream start codon where protein synthesis is initiated. Depending on the origin of the cell-free extract, a Shine–Dalgarno (prokaryote) or Kozak (eukaryote) sequence is used to initiate

translation. The open reading frame frequently starts with a protein detection tag such as the RGS-His6 tag or the FLAG tag, followed by the library of binding proteins and a spacer protein. The spacer should provide the displayed library the flexibility to fold outside of the ribosome tunnel (at least 23–30 amino acids). This fusion construct lacks a stop codon at the mRNA level, thus preventing release of the mRNA and the polypeptide from the ribosome. High concentrations of magnesium and low temperature further stabilize the ternary complex [Hoogenboom 2005, Zahnd et al. 2007].

Transcription and translation in ribosome display can be performed simultaneously in a one-step process, with coupled transcription and translation under the same conditions, or separately in two steps: uncoupled transcription and translation. The one-step system usually consists of a eukaryotic rabbit reticulocyte or systems based on reconstituted highly purified components, PURE system [Knamori et al. 2014], two-step system employs prokaryotic *E. coli* S30 extract [He & Taussig 2007]. This strategy avoids problems of mRNA degradation using prepared extracts based on the RNase I deficient strain *E. coli* MRE600 [Schaffitzel et al. 1999]. Exo- and endonucleases originating from natural extracts rapidly degrade library mRNA during the in vitro translation procedure at 37°C during ribosome display, and mRNA–ribosome–protein complexes need to be kept cold in the presence of RNase inhibitors. Additionally, *E. coli* shows an SsrA RNA mediated mechanism to rescue stalled ribosomes and tag the translated protein for proteolytic degradation. To neutralize this reaction, an oligonucleotide complementary to SsrA RNA can be added to the *E. coli* extract [Galan et al. 2016].

Complexes, which are formed during in vitro translation, can directly be used to select for the properties of the displayed protein [Amstutz et al. 2001]. Since all steps of ribosome display are carried out entirely in vitro, reaction conditions of individual steps can be tailored to the requirements of the protein species investigated and the objectives of the selection or evolution experiment. There are several prerequisites for successful ribosome display: (i) suitable genetic diversification techniques, (ii) functional expression of the genetic variants and (iii) effective selection of protein variants.

Ribosome display is a potent tool that has demonstrated its value in many areas. In the past two decades, ribosome display has been gaining great attention from scientists from

different fields because of its unique advantages compared to other display technologies. The broad application fields of this technology include antibody engineering, proteomics, diagnostics, and therapeutics. Because ribosome display avoids the problems of cytotoxicity, soluble protein expression and secretion bias in cell-based systems, it could be an ideal means by which to display functional (single chain) proteins for drug discovery applications like target discovery and functional identification.

Plückthun's group [Jermutus et al. 2001] as one of the first described an application of increasing concentration of reducing agents in selection step to select molecules stable under these conditions. They used dithiothreitol (DTT), which was added during translation and to washing buffer. This approach was selected to evolve thermodynamic stability of single-chain Fv antibody fragments (scFvs), which contain disulphide bridges that are crucial for their stability and activity. Mutant molecules could survive the selection process only if they folded correctly in the presence of DTT and retained their target binding activity. After five rounds of evolution selected mutants exhibited an improved stability and 30-fold improved affinity compared to their wild type.

Selection pressure could be applied also posttranslationally. Matsuura and Plückthun [2003] demonstrated that ribosome display selections with hydrophobic interaction chromatography (HIC) matrixes at increased temperature could selectively remove aggregation-prone peptides. HIC is a technique for the separation of bio-molecules based on the hydrophobic attraction between the HIC matrix and the protein molecules. HIC is sensitive enough to interact with nonpolar groups normally buried within the tertiary structure of the protein, that are exposed due to incorrect folding. This technique enables the removal of molecules that are misfolded, for example after following translation with DTT, and molecules that are kinetically unstable or prone to aggregation and have exposed hydrophobic patches.

Buchanan and colleagues [Buchanan et al. 2012] demonstrated that by combination of ribosome display with appropriate selection pressure it is possible to improve stability of proteins. Their research focused on the two therapeutic proteins with known drug development issues- Granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF) and erythropoietin (EPO). G-CSF stimulates the production of white blood cells, and it is used as a treatment to

accelerate recovery from neutropaenia in patients after chemotherapy treatment. However, it cannot be expressed soluble in *Escherichia coli* and therefore needs to be refolded from inclusion bodies, requiring a more complicated and expensive manufacturing process. EPO increases red blood cell production, and it is an approved treatment for anaemia. Normally this protein is produced soluble in mammalian cell cultures. However, EPO is a thermodynamically unstable protein that is prone to aggregation at elevated temperatures and has an unstable intermediate species. The challenge of improving the stability and expression levels of proteins relates to the process of folding. To create a robust stability selection pressure to select proteins with required properties they combined three previously used factors, the reducing agent DTT, elevated temperature and HIC matrixes to destabilise and remove misfolded variants. With combination of these factors and ribosome display they were able to enhance stability EPO and G-CSF and retained functional activity. Also selected G-CSF variants demonstrated a 1000-fold improvement in soluble expression compared to the wild-type.

Douthwaite et al. [Douthwaite et al. 2016] also used combination of DTT, increased temperature and HIC to optimize affinity and long-term stability of cytotoxic T lymphocyte-associated protein 4 (CTLA4). This protein is a membrane receptor that function as negative regulator of immune response of T cell after binding of ligand CD80 and CD86. After fusion to modified human IgG1 Fc region act as approved therapeutic protein for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. After five rounds of ribosome display they were able to select mutants with greater stability and increased affinity to CD80 and CD86. These mutants exhibit a significantly improved safety profile over other injectable therapies in rheumatoid arthritis, and benefits from lower and more infrequent doses because of the enhanced affinity and long-term stability in room temperature.

Group of Christian Löw [Custódio et al. 2021] focused on actual topic and report the selection of single-domain antibodies (also called nanobodies) from a synthetic library, which target and neutralize the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. Combination of two screening method- ribosome display and phage display was used in this study to decrease a diversity of the library after several rounds. Nanobodies were selected against biotinylated RBC in one round of ribosome display followed by two rounds of phage

display. As a result, several mutants were selected and expressed in *E. coli*, purified *via* metal-affinity chromatography to high purity and after that characterized. Selected nanobodies bound RBD with nanomolar affinities, and all of them presented higher thermal stability compared to classical antibodies. Also, Chen et al. [Chen et al. 2021] aimed to select nanobodies for (RBD) of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein, but they developed a cell-free nanobody engineering platform (CeVICA) that uses ribosome display for in vitro selection of nanobodies from a library of randomized nanobodies sequences and computational binder prediction using CDR-directed clustering analysis. As an input for nanobodies selection they used highly diverse library with size of 1010 mutants, and after three selection rounds of ribosome display, they were able to select 30 mutants with increased binding and neutralization to RBD of SARS-CoV-2. Furthermore, most of these mutants showed very good resistance to thermal denaturation and were able to efficiently refold after complete thermal denaturation. Such high refolding capability may be partly explained using ribosome display for the selection of these nanobodies. During selection round nanobodies must fold into their functional confirmation while tethered to ribosomes in a minimally reconstituted protein synthesis environment that lacks factors, such as chaperones, normally found inside cells to aid protein folding, thus enriching for nanobodies with strong inherent folding stability. In both studies selected nanobodies showed very good biophysical properties that are comparable with antibodies developed by other techniques and suggested them as an alternative for development of new type of a cure for COVID-19.

Finlay et al. [Finlay et al. 2009] also directed to the improving characteristics of antibodies. They focused on the antibodies that neutralize interaction between RAGE (receptor for advanced glycation end products) and its ligand and could have potential therapeutic applications in acute and chronic diseases. Firstly, they breded rat form of anti-RAGE monoclonal antibody which was subsequently humanized. This antibody was efficient in vivo in acute sepsis, but for human usage it was essential to be improve its affinity. As a method to reach this goal they used random and targeted mutagenesis in combination with phage and ribosome display technologies. Thanks to this approach they were able to identify a number of variants that had improved affinity for human RAGE while maintaining the functionally relevant epitope and the required cross-reactivity to the mouse RAGE, which is required for

preclinical studies. This broad mutational scanning approach has given insight into key residues that mediate interaction of antibodies with RAGE and identified multiple possible mutational hotspots. Moreover, during the sequence analysis it was observed that several mutations were accumulated in the flexible linker that connected light and heavy chain of antibody. Considering other published studies, these mutations could possibly have an indirect role in improving antibody binding to RAGE through enhanced solubility, improved folding, and optimized antibody orientation during binding.

Antibody scFv fragments were also the first complex library with which ribosome display was tested not just for selection but also for affinity maturation. Jackson's group [Groves et al. 2006] highlighted advantages of using ribosome display for affinity maturation compared to other selection method- phage display on an example of antibodies for binders to bovine insulin. Population of antibodies, enriched by phage display was subjected to simultaneous stringent selections using phage or ribosome display, with reduction of antigen concentration at each round. Between each round of selection, diversity of library was also enhanced by introducing random mutation by PCR with Taq polymerase. As a result, ribosome display selections generated antibodies with enhanced affinity compared with those obtained from phage display and which was unrelated to parental population of antibodies. This result illustrated the potential for ribosome display to select a different population of antibodies compared to phage display. Sequence analysis of selected clones by ribosome display with improved binding properties presented some mutagenesis hotspots but also loss of disulphide bridges in a structure of antibodies which could lead to reduced stability as show Plückthun's group before.

Béhar et al. [Béhar et al. 2019] developed Affitins, a solid class of affinity proteins which could be used as substitutes to antibodies or to complement them. They report the generation and characterization of anti-bacterial Affitins with high specificity for *Staphylococcus aureus*. In this study ribosome display selections were carried-out using whole-living-cell and native combinatorial libraries, which avoid production of protein targets and immunization of animals. The analysis of selected mutant showed exclusive recognition of *S. aureus* among dozens of other bacterial strains, and also higher thermostability compared to the wild type

the protein. Results suggested that this class of reagents can be useful in future diagnostic and biomedical applications.

Lorey et al. [Lorey et al. 2014] research aimed to scaffold-based technology as a possibility to overcome limitations of classical monoclonal antibodies. This group identified ubiquitin as an ideal scaffold protein for the possible generation of binding proteins specifically targeted to tumor cells, able carry effector molecules such as toxins, cytokines, or radiolabels to their intended site of action. Ubiquitin is a small protein with outstanding biochemical and biophysical properties. It is mainly known as a cytosolic protein involved in numerous intracellular regulatory processes, but it also circulates in the blood of healthy humans in significant concentrations. This higher level of ubiquitin in serum of healthy persons point on decreased half-life of extracellular ubiquitin compared to the intracellular form. This could be problem to yield high tumor accumulation while maintaining low levels in healthy tissues and blood, the half-life of this molecules needs to be extended. To improve these features, they used combination of phage display, ribosome display and ELISA to select molecules with highest affinity, thermal stability, and solubility. The selection was performed with dimeric ubiquitin library and after four rounds of phage display and four round of ribosome display with applied selection pressure during selection over each cycle they used ELISA to identify most soluble and thermostable mutants. Selected peptides, so-called affilin molecules, exhibited improved stability in solution at higher concentration without forming aggregates. Also, thermal and serum stability was improved, and long-term test showed extended half-life from hour to days. This ubiquitin-based scaffold technology holds promising perspectives for therapeutic indications requiring specific product profiles.

Šakanović et al. [Šakanović et al. 2020] reported a high-throughput approach for the selection of peripheral protein domains that bind specifically to cholesterol in lipid membranes. Specific lipid recognition and the subsequent recruitment of peripheral proteins to cellular sites enable crucial biological processes and represent core molecular mechanisms that enable attack and defense by cellular and pathogen associated proteins. Moreover, in chemical biology, lipid targeting by small protein domains is needed for targeted localization of proteins to subcellular compartments or model lipid vesicles and it represents a widely used approach to study the distribution and metabolism of various cellular lipids. As a model

peripheral domain was selected domain 4 of perfringolysin O, a cholesterol-dependent cytolysin from bacterium *Clostridium perfringens*. This domain secure specific binding to cholesterol-containing lipid membranes. Primarily, gene library was developed consisting of seven degenerated codons. After four selection rounds of ribosome display against cholesterol-containing small unilamellar vesicles immobilized on streptavidin-coated magnetic beads, selected mutants were characterized. Almost all selected mutants exhibited equal or higher binding ability to cholesterol-lipid vesicles compare to wild type. Observed higher affinity could be consequence of increased hydrophobic character of mutants by predominant hydrophobic substitutions of aminoacids. Developed approach provides an effective platform for a comprehensive study of protein lipid interactions and for development of engineered lipid binding domains for other applications.

Li et al. [Li et al. 2021] focused on establishing of ribosome display in agriculture. The point of their interest was paraquat- widely used quaternary nitrogen herbicide, extremely toxic for humans. Chronic exposure to the paraquat significantly increases a risk for developing Parkinson's disease. They attempted to generate a new class of receptor proteins called "anticalins" based on lipocalins, a large family of extracellular proteins, which would be able to recognize paraquat even in a very small concentration. After generation of protein library and five rounds of ribosome display, selected mutants were analysed. Result showed not only improvement of affinity of mutants to paraquat compared to wild-type. Lipocalins had in general large tendency to aggregate during expression. Analyse of selected mutants additionally also exhibit increased solubility of selected lipocalin mutants.

2.1. Affinity maturation

Ribosome display allows the selection for affinity, stability, solubility, and enzymatic activity, but the most powerful applications of this technology is the rapid isolation and direct evolution of specific high-affinity binders with desired properties. Generally, protein affinity is a key parameter that often regulates the biological function of the bound complex and high binding affinity is a desired characteristic of proteins used for therapeutic applications and in biotechnology. Ribosome display have allowed selection for binding proteins to a wide variety

of targets, such as small compounds, peptides, whole proteins [Jermutus et al. 2001, Hanes et al. 1998, Hanes et al. 2000, Irving et al. 2001, Li et al. 2019] or alternative protein scaffolds (Rothe et al. 2006). Employment of ribosome display in antibody development have generated high-performance binders against nearly any antigen of interest.

Binders can be affinity matured by randomly or directly introducing mutations into genes using PCR-based mutagenesis. By displaying and selecting these new mutant libraries over many cycles, binders with enhanced characteristics can be identified. Mutations can be carried out within the RT-PCR recovery after the selection procedure, inserting mutations in a designed, semirandom or random way [Rothe et al. 2006]. Protein selection and maturation are achieved either with increasing cycles of washing (Figure 3, step 8), decreasing

Figure 4. The principle of molecular evolution as performed by in vitro ribosome display. The selection process of a library pool leads to the stepwise improvement of the binding characteristics against a given ligand serving as a target for affinity maturation. By alternating the selection and recovery, the isolation of high-affinity biologicals with binding specificity to the ligand can be achieved [Rothe et al. 2006].

concentrations of purified antigens captured on coated magnetic beads or microtitre plates or by off-rate selection [Zahnd et al. 2007]. Affinity enhancement or maturation traditionally implies the improvement of an existing low-affinity binder (Figure 4). Typically, binders isolated from naïve or synthetic libraries have low affinities in the micromolar range and require further enhancement through affinity maturation to be useful in therapeutic or

diagnostic applications [Rothe et al. 2006]. Ribosome display technology for single chain variable fragment optimisation has one of the most powerful display ranges (typically 10^{12} molecules) and the advantage of being performed entirely *in vitro* [Galan et al. 2016].

Ribosome display technology was used for the first time exactly for affinity maturation. Professor Plückthun and his colleague [Hanes & Plückthun 1997] selected a single-chain fragment (scFv) of an antibody enriched by five cycles of ribosome display. The selected scFv fragments acquired up to four unrelated amino acid exchanges over the five generations, but they remained fully compatible with antigen binding. Since then, libraries of native folded proteins could have been screened and made to evolve in a cell-free system without any transformation or constraints imposed by the host cell.

One of the early works, in which ribosome display was used demonstrated that *in vitro* display technology has great potential for the maturation of high-affinity protein binders. Plückthun's group [Hanes et al. 2000] isolated picomolar affinity scFvs from a synthetic naïve library by combining the off-rate selection and evolution power of ribosome display. The authors selected a range of different scFvs with affinities up to 82 pM from a fully synthetic naïve antibody scFv library. All the selected antibodies accumulated beneficial mutations throughout the selection cycles. In the off-rate selection, a pool of polypeptides is bound to an immobilized ligand. By adding an excess of free ligand, every dissociating library member will be immediately trapped. After incubation, only those binders with the lowest off-rate will remain bound to the immobilized antigen. Thus, increasing the incubation time with the competitive ligand increases the selection pressure applied. As the on rate normally only changes within a relatively small window, lowering the off-rate will result in increased binding affinity. This work demonstrated that ribosome display not only allows the selection of library members but also further evolves them, thereby mimicking the strategy of the immune system. Using such off-rate selections, Jermutus et al. [Jermutus et al. 2001] were able to improve an antiferredin scFv that already had a high initial affinity of 1.1 nM. By combining ribosome display with DNA shuffling the authors improved an scFv 30-fold to a final affinity of 40 pM. Using the same strategy, anti-prion binding scFvs fragment was evolved to affinity of 1 picomolar range [Luginbühl et al. 2006].

Immunoglobulins had long been considered as the obvious first choice for obtaining affinity reagents. This notion was challenged by the development of new type affinity tools, which have emerged from the successful engineering of proteins belonging to various

Figure 5. Protein scaffolds that were successfully displayed on ribosomes and applied to selection for novel binders or affinity maturation. Colours are according to secondary structure. Helices are red, beta sheets are cyan, turns are green, and coils are white. PDB IDs used to generate this figure are given in brackets. (A) Nogo-66 receptor (1P8T); (B) Tenth fibronectin type III domain (1TTG); (C) Designed ankyrin repeat protein (1SVX); (D) scFv (1MOE); (E) Bovine heart fatty acid binding protein (1BWY); (F) Llama VHH domain (1I3V); (G) Human CTLA-4 (1I8L) [Rothe et al. 2006].

structural classes [Nygren & Skerra 2004]. Proteins appearing suitable for the development of such artificial affinity reagents have been collectively termed scaffold proteins and ribosome display has become popular for the display and evolution of such compounds (Figure 5) [Rothe et al. 2006, Zahnd et al. 2007].

Although ribosome display technology was first reported more than 20 years ago [Hanes & Plüncckthun 1997] and it has provided new opportunities over other display technologies, it has not become as popular as phage display. Prominent reason for that was the preparation difficulty of the stable ternary complex in the cell-free protein synthesis system. Because *E. coli* S30 extract contains endogenous components such as proteases and nucleases, degradation of mRNA and nascent polypeptide reduces a stability of the mRNA-ribosome-polypeptide ternary complex. Furthermore, incomplete information of components within

cell extract makes it difficult to optimize the system for ribosome display. For that reason, Ueda and colleagues have tested an improved, highly controllable cell-free translation system called the protein synthesizing using recombinant elements (PURE) system [Shinizu et al. 2001, 2005]. Because the PURE system is reconstructed by using only the essential purified factors and enzymes responsible for gene expression in *E. coli*, it contains no nucleases and proteases. PURE system was successfully employed also for ribosome display technology and its application in antibody development showed that PURE ribosome display is more efficient than the conventional method [Kanamori et al. 2014].

Ribosome display has proven to be a powerful *in vitro* selection and evolution method for generating high-affinity binders from libraries of folded proteins. It works entirely *in vitro*, and this has two important consequences. First, since no transformation of any cells is required, libraries with much greater diversity can be handled than with most other techniques. Second, since a library does not have to be cloned and transformed, it is very convenient to introduce random errors in the library by PCR-based methods and select improved binders. Thus, a true directed evolution, an iteration between randomization and selection over several generations, can be conveniently carried out, e.g., for affinity maturation, either on a given clone or on the whole library.

2.1.1. The case of staphylokinase

Ribosome display technique had been successfully established in our laboratory. We have applied it for engineering of several different protein properties, among which one was affinity maturation of staphylokinase to plasmin.

Bacterial staphylokinase (SAK) has been studied as a promising third-generation drug in the treatment for vascular occlusion. Mature SAK is a 136 amino acid (15.5 kDa) single chain extracellular protein secreted by lysogenic strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*). SAK works as an indirect plasminogen activator, which means that itself it does not have any enzymatic activity, but it forms 1:1 stoichiometric complex with plasmin that activates other plasminogen molecules. In human plasma, SAK binds with greater affinity to fibrin-bound

plasmin or plasminogen than to circulating enzymes (Collen 1998). While SAK-plasmin complex is enzymatically active, complex SAK-plasminogen is inactive and it cannot serve as a plasminogen activator [Toul et al. 2021] (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Extended mechanism of staphylokinase. The extended mechanism newly includes binding of staphylokinase (SAK) to plasminogen (Plg) to form an inactive complex, not capable of plasminogen-to-plasmin (Plg-to-Plm) conversion and having a significant effect on the overall effectivity. The mechanism further includes a newly identified two-step induced-fit binding mechanism for both Plm and Plg binding by SAK leading to conformationally modified forms, designated by asterisk, of the proteins. The Plm* form is more active than the Plm form [Toul et al. 2021].

High affinity for fibrin without causing bleeding complications and low production costs makes SAK a promising thrombolytic agent. However, currently there are some constrictions causing that SAK cannot be used in clinical practice. Due to the non-human origin, it triggers an immune response [Collen 1998]. Half-life of SAK was showed to be 6.3 minutes [Vanderschueren et al. 1996]. Such half – life is relatively short compared to 30-45 minutes of some engineered thrombolytics [Mican et al. 2019]. Additionally, SAK is highly fibrin specific, but it has fewer fibrinolytic properties than streptokinase [Nedaenia et al. 2020]. As a result, there is a continuous need to improve SAKs properties.

Strategies for improving SAK include reducing immunogenicity, increasing half-life and stability, improving clot penetration, and reducing risk of re-occlusion. Our approach primarily

lies in improving SAKs affinity for plasmin, which in our opinion will lead to improvement of other properties such as lower immunogenicity, increased half-life, or improved clot penetration.

The first step in the development of SAK ribosome display was synthesis of combinatorial library. SAK library was synthesized by error-prone PCR, the most common procedure for creating genetic variation. This technique involves amplifying of the gene in the presence of manganese ions or nucleotide analogues such as 8-oxo-guanosine or dPTP to promote the misincorporation of nucleotides by the DNA polymerase, or by using a low fidelity DNA polymerase such as Taq polymerase. The mutational load can be adapted by increasing the number of amplification cycles or by increasing the concentration of dNTP analogues. The optimal mutational load depends on the library, especially its tolerance to mutations, and the final application [Zahnd et al. 2007]. We used combination of dNTP analogues with Taq polymerase. We synthesized three different libraries (Figure 5; L1, L2 and L3) with various dNTPs analogue concentrations. After DNA sequence analysis and determination of average number of single nucleotide polymorphism (SNPs) for each library, we selected combination of two libraries (L1 and L2) for SAK ribosome display.

Figure 7. Quality control of synthesized SAK libraries. Wild type SAK PCR amplicons has length of 428bp. Synthesized libraries should be the same length but should contain new mutations introduced during error-prone PCR. As seen in the picture, all three libraries have appropriate length. Distribution of mutations was examined by sequence analysis. Visualization by ethidium bromide staining; 1 % agarose gel.

Subsequently, we optimized binding of plasmin to microtiterate plate. As described in the Figure 3, the mRNA-ribosome-SAK ternary complexes are used for affinity selection on an immobilized plasmin. For ligand immobilization, we used the Nunc Immobilizer Amino Plates

and commercially available human plasmin. For creation of SAK-plasmin complex, it was important that plasmin carboxy-terminus was exposed in solution, therefore this type of coupling was ideal for plasmin immobilization. Attaching of plasmin to the surface was realized according to the manufacturer's instructions and the presence of plasmin after protein coupling was tested by BCA assay (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Examination of plasmin attachment to a microtiter plate. Attachment of plasmin to the plate surface after overnight incubation at 4°C was examined by colorimetric BCA assay kit. Presence of the plasmin on the plate surface is indicated by a purple coloration of the BCA reagent. NC – negative control, well without plasmin; Plm – well with plasmin.

As already mentioned, one of the basic preconditions for good RD results are highly active ribosomes. Cell-free protein synthesis extract can be homemade, prepared from *E. coli* in the laboratory, known as S30 extract, or can be purchased in the more purified form as a PURE system. For ribosome display optimization, we prepared homemade S30 extract, and we also purchased commercially available PURE system. For S30 extract preparation, we used low RNase I activity *E. coli* strain MRE600. Cells were lysed by a single pass through an Avestin Emulsiflex C-5 high-pressure homogenizer at 17 000 psi. The cell lysate was clarified by centrifugation at 30 000 g and supernatant was incubated at 37°C (250 rpm, 1 hour). Subsequently, supernatant was either dialyzed at cut off 6-8kDa or not dialyzed (Figure 9).

Figure 9. S30 ribosome extract preparation.

Ribosomal activity was measured by beta-lactamase assay (Figure 10). Most active ribosomes were obtained by dialysis of ribosome extract resulting in twice as much hydrolyzed nitrocefin molecules in beta-lactamase assay than achieved with control active ribosomes. With undialyzed extract, we reached only one tenth of control activity. Most active form of ribosomes was later used for SAK ribosome display.

Figure 11. Beta-lactamase assay. The protocol is based on the hydrolysis of the substrate nitrocefin, a chromogenic cephalosporin, that results in the generation of a coloured product detectable at 490 nm, which is directly proportional to the amount of beta-lactamase activity. Beta-lactamase was synthesized in vitro using new ribosome extract. RE – ribosome extract.

Optimization of ribosome display was performed with wild type (WT) SAK gene, instead of library, since using library usually results in weaker yields of eluted mRNA. Except for minor changes, the procedure was based on the published protocol designed for in vitro selection and evolution of protein specifically bind to a target [Zahnd et al. 2007]. Each test started with 10 µg of input mRNA; this corresponds to -1.5×10^{13} molecules [Zahnd et al. 2007]. The input mRNA was subjected to a single round of affinity selection: translation in vitro, capture of ribosome complexes on immobilized target ligand, and release of mRNA. Method for SAK ribosome display was as follows (Figure 3): The day before ribosome display itself, a WT SAK gene in the form of a PCR products was ligated into the vector specially designed for ribosome display (pRDV plasmid). The gene for SAK was in this way genetically fused to a sequence providing a promoter and translation initiation region and tolA spacer sequence, important for tethering newly synthesized protein to ribosome. The final ribosome display construct was obtained by PCR amplification of the SAK insert and flanking regions from the ligated plasmid.

Reaction products were analyzed by agarose gel electrophoresis and PCR products were extracted by DNA gel purification kit. Human plasmin was attached to the microtiterate plate during overnight incubation at 4°C. In vitro transcription of extracted PCR products yielded mRNA that was used for in vitro translation using S30 *E. coli* extract. During translation, mRNA-ribosome-SAK ternary complex was created, and the ribosome did not release the properly folded protein because it did not have a stop codon. The mRNA-ribosome-SAK ternary complexes were used for affinity selection on an immobilized plasmin. After washing, mRNA of bound ternary complex was eluted. The retained ribosome complexes were dissociated with ice-cold elution buffer for 10 min in the cold room, and released mRNA was recovered by using the Rneasy kit. Afterwards, mRNA was reverse transcribed and amplified by PCR. All steps after in vitro translation and before reverse transcription were strictly processed at 4°C, to prevent ternary complex from disintegration. After first round of WT SAK ribosome display, we did not obtain expected results, so whole process needed to be carefully optimized, but after adjustment of conditions for several steps in SAK ribosome display we achieved positive results (Figure 11) and we developed a method that could be applied for selection of SAK variants from a synthesized library.

Figure 11. Results of the wild type SAK ribosome display. Visualization of PCR products after final reverse transcription and PCR reaction (Figure 3, step 10) on an agarose gel. Reverse transcription is performed with (+) and without (-) reverse transcriptase (RT), to check for DNA contamination. NC- negative control: mRNA from wells with bovine serum albumin (BSA); I – input mRNA: mRNA used for in vitro translation; L – mRNA eluted from wells with ligand (plasmin); RT – reverse transcriptase. Visualization by ethidium bromide staining; 1.5% agarose gel.

At this point, the success of the selection was demonstrated by stronger band of PCR product obtained from a target-containing well (L+RT) in comparison with that from a non-target containing well (NC+RT). In fact, this is what we (reproducibly) obtained after first rounds of ribosome display with wild type. The obtained result is of critical importance

because it demonstrates that we were able successfully immobilize the ligand and perform the specific selection of the wild type SAK. The obtained preliminary results clearly indicated feasibility of SAK evolving by ribosome display. On the other hand, these results imply an importance for optimization of the selection round to increase enrichment of the selectively bound SAK and get rid of DNA the presence of which is demonstrated by a band in the line I-RT.

With the optimized SAK ribosome display protocol, we proceeded to SAK ribosome display with the library. In the first round of ribosome display, we successfully selected SAK variants (Figure 12 and Figure 14, 1st round). The success of selection was confirmed by DNA sequencing of several different bacterial colonies after *E. coli* transformation with the library obtained after 1st SAK ribosome display round. After first round, we were able to select SAK variants that acquired up to 5 unrelated amino acids changes in SAK gene, but at this point we did not observe any mutation clustering.

Figure 12. Amino-acid sequence alignment after 1st round of SAK ribosome display with library.

With such promising results we wanted to proceed to 2nd round of ribosome display, but we started to have a problem with the amplification of reversely transcribed mRNA – cDNA (Figure 13, A) and we could not acquire enough amount of input DNA for 2nd ribosome display round. Although the PCR reaction in molecular biology is considered as a relatively simple method, there are pitfalls that complicate the reaction producing spurious results. Since PCR conditions that we were using for initial PCR reactions worked well and we were obtaining PCR products with required length and good quality, (Figures 7 and 9), we initially assumed

that we are dealing with mRNA degradation after mRNA elution. Upon careful examination of the agarose gels, we noticed that in some samples, after the final ribosome display PCR reaction, there was ladder-like pattern (Figure 14, 1st round, samples NC- and I-). We went through the available literature and found out that such PCR profile may occur due to the intrinsic properties of primers or because of repeated library amplification [Tolle et al. 2014]. Such information led us to hypothesis, that we are not seeing mRNA degradation, but PCR by-products and we started to re-optimize PCR conditions for SAK library amplification. We started with adjustment of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and magnesium ions concentrations in PCR reaction [Figure 13, B]. We observed that under certain conditions (Condition 3), products of PCR reaction are not fully smeared, but we could see ladder-like pattern. This analysis led us further to optimization of primer [Figure 13, C] and Vent polymerase concentration (data not shown). Lastly, we monitored the dependence of the PCR profile on the concentration of the input cDNA [Figure 13, D]. With such an optimized PCR condition, we were able to amplify

Figure 13. PCR optimization of SAK library amplification. Ribosome display – cDNA obtained from 1st round of SAK ribosome display, 5 different PCR reactions; Ctrl 1 and 2 – input mRNA reversely transcribed and amplified; WT – wild type SAK gene. Visualization by ethidium bromide staining; 1.5% agarose gel.

a cDNA product from ribosome display of the desired size in sufficient quantity, although the PCR product was not completely pure. We discovered that in our case results of the PCR reaction are caused by primer sequence and depend mainly on the concentration of the input DNA. If the DNA concentration is high enough, the PCR product is pure. However, if the

concentration of the input DNA is low, which happens often in ribosome display, the primers start to react with each other and form a ladder-like structure. We could not change the primer sequence because they must precisely define the beginning and the end of the SAK gene and contain sequences for certain endonucleases, therefore, for subsequent rounds of ribosome display it was important to decrease concentrations of primers, dNTPs and polymerase and use as much input cDNA as possible.

After optimisation of reaction condition for PCR, we continued with 2nd and 3rd round of SAK ribosome display. The selection pressure was exerted by increasing the number of washing steps after binding of ternary complex to plasmin. While in the first round we washed the plate only once, in the third round we increased the number of washes to nine. As can be seen in Figure 14, increasing the number of washing steps completely suppressed non-specific

Figure 14. Results of the SAK ribosome display with library after 1st, 2nd and 3rd round. Visualization of PCR products after final reverse transcription and PCR reaction (Step 10, Figure 1) on an agarose gel. Reverse transcription is performed with (+) and without (-) reverse transcriptase (RT), to check for DNA contamination. NC- negative control: mRNA from wells with bovine serum albumin (BSA); I - input mRNA: mRNA used for in vitro translation; L - mRNA eluted from wells with ligand (plasmin); RT - reverse transcriptase, x wash - number of washing steps after ligation of ternary complex to plasmin.

binding (3rd round, NC+). After the third round of selection, the PCR products were ligated into a vector, which was used to transform *E. coli*, and single clones were analysed. After evaluating the sequencing results, we will decide on the next step. The presented protocol has been optimized for *E. coli* S30 translation systems. We are considering introducing SAK ribosome

display selection using the PURE system, in which we could gain better yields. So far, we can conclude that established protocol executed by binding and elution from immobilized plasmin, is clearly operating.

2.2. Increasing solubility of membrane proteins – the case of GPCR

G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) are cell surface receptors that mediate the cellular responses to an enormous diversity of endogenous signaling molecules such as hormones and neurotransmitters, as well as environmental signals such as pheromones, smells, taste and light. The ligands detected by members of the GPCRs family range from peptides and protein hormones (e.g. angiotensin, bradykinin, endothelin, melanocortin), biogenic amines (e.g. adrenaline, dopamine, histamine, serotonin), and lipids and eicosanoids (e.g. cannabinoids, leukotrienes, prostaglandines, thromboxanes), nucleotides and nucleosides (e.g. adenosine, ADP, ATP, UTP) and a wide variety of other molecules down to Ca^{2+} ions and photons (light).

The overall structural features of the GPCRs family are highly conserved: all of these receptors contain seven hydrophobic domains, postulated to span the plasma membrane, connected by hydrophilic extracellular and intracellular loops. The family of GPCRs is also known as the family of the 7-helix transmembrane receptors (7TM) due to the common appearance of 7 transmembrane helices or the serpentine receptors, pointing to the serpentine-like configuration of trans-membrane helices. Although GPCRs share a common

Figure 15. Structure and topology of GPCRs [Latoracca et al. 2016].

membrane topology, they are remarkably diverse in sequence and specially in the size of the extracellular amino-terminal tails, cytoplasmic loops, and carboxy-terminal tails [Klabunde & Hessler 2002, Latoracca et al. 2016]. The majority of the primary sequence homology resides within the hydrophobic transmembrane domain, whereas the hydrophilic loop regions are more divergent.

As the name of the proteins suggests, GPCRs act primarily through the activation of ubiquitous guanine nucleotide-binding regulatory proteins: so called G-proteins. The signaling mechanism of these heterotrimeric G-proteins depends on the dissociation of their α -subunit from the β - and γ -subunit complex, stimulated by the exchange of guanine nucleotide diphosphate for guanine nucleotide triphosphate on the G-protein α -subunit. GTP-bound G-protein α -subunits or $\beta\gamma$ complexes initiate intracellular signaling responses by acting on effector molecules such as adenylate cyclases or phospholipases or by direct regulation of ion channels or kinase function [Gutkind 1998, Wettschureck & Offermanns 2005, Marinissen & Gutkin 2001] (Figure 16).

With about 800 different members in humans, GPCRs are the largest superfamily of cell surface receptors [Fredriksson et al. 2003]. The principal role of GPCRs is reflected by the great number of human diseases linked to aberrant GPCR signalling, including metabolic disorders, cardiovascular diseases, mental disorders, neurodegenerative diseases, and cancer [Heng et al. 2013]. As a consequence, GPCRs represent highly relevant drug targets, and about 30 – 50% of the currently marketed drugs act on these receptors [Overington et al. 2006, Lagerström & Schiöth 2008, Okuno et al. 2008].

Much of our understanding about GPCRs has been obtained from the recent successes in structural investigations of these proteins. However, the 70 unique GPCR structures deposited in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) to date still represent less than 10% of all receptors [Congreve et al. 2020]. Furthermore, after a period of success between 2010 and 2013 (19 unique GPCR structures solved), the number of unique GPCR structures published per year decreased during the last few years (4 unique GPCR structures solved per year). This trend reflects a fact that the problems limiting structural investigations of GPCRs still have not been completely

resolved. The major challenges in such investigations are the difficulties to produce functional GPCRs in sufficient yields as well as their inherent instability.

Figure 16. Diversity of G-protein-coupled receptors. A wide variety of ligands, including biogenic amines, amino acids, ions, lipids, peptides and proteins, use GPCRs to stimulate cytoplasmic and nuclear targets through heterotrimeric G-protein-dependent and -independent pathways. Such signaling pathways regulate key biological functions such as cell proliferation, cell survival and angiogenesis. Abbreviations: DAG, diacylglycerol; FSH, follicle-stimulating hormone; GEF, guanine nucleotide exchange factor; LH, leuteinizing hormone; LPA, lysophosphatidic acid; PAF, platelet-activating factor; PI3K, phosphoinositide 3-kinase; PKC, protein kinase C; PLC, phospholipase C; S1P, sphingosine-1-phosphate; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone [Marinissen & Gutkin 2001].

Over 30% of human genes encode membrane proteins and an astounding 39 of the top 50 prescription drugs sold in U.S.A. in 2010 (78%) mediate their pharmaceutical actions by targeting various integral membrane proteins. Despite the major clinical relevance of integral membrane proteins, less than 1% of Protein Data Bank entries are integral membrane protein structures [Salon et al. 2011], and most of them are of bacterial origin. Comparatively little is known about how membrane proteins function and how their structure is determined by the amino acid sequence. The great disparity between our understanding of the properties of soluble proteins and membrane proteins has occurred largely because of the many practical

problems of working with membrane proteins. Low expression levels, toxicity to cells, inability to refold from solubilized non-native aggregates in vitro, difficulties in purification, limited stability in detergent-solubilized form, and heterogeneity of detergent-solubilized form, i.e. properties affected mainly by low solubility, are major problems in effort of crystallization and solving structure of integral membrane proteins. The low solubility is a serious problem in characterizing also non-membrane proteins. In fact, up to 80% of non-membrane proteins that have been identified so far are unsuitable for structural studies due to their low solubility [Christendat et al. 2000]. Similar problems related to poor protein solubility occur in the pharmaceutical industry, where it has been estimated that more than 90% of all potential protein-based pharmaceuticals are unsuitable for pre-clinical or clinical development due to low solubility [Caldwell et al. 2001].

Structural comparisons of water-soluble and membrane proteins support a unifying view of protein structure in which the structural organization of water-soluble and membrane proteins reflect variations on the same themes. In particular, membrane and water-soluble proteins exhibit similarities in: (i) protein surface area [Israelachvili 1985], (ii) packing density of buried atoms [Rees et al. 1989a], and (iii) the relative average hydrophobicity of buried residues [Rees et al. 1989b]. These findings suggest that from protein stability point of view, changing the lipid-exposed residues of a membrane protein for polar and charged residues might not result in a significantly destabilized protein. This is supported by findings of Pace's group that showed that certain amino acids increase solubility of protein RNase Sa without affecting its stability [Shaw et al. 2001, Trevino et al. 2007].

In the CasProt project, we propose to replace the lipid-exposed hydrophobic residues within the transmembrane domains of GPCRs with more hydrophilic residues to engineer water-soluble variants of GPCRs capable of folding in aqueous solutions. The ultimate test of this proposal would be to render a membrane protein water soluble by mutating only surface residues. The importance of generating improved receptor analogs for atomic-resolution biophysical studies and drug design cannot be overstated. In fact, this proof-of-concept has already been presented on the solubilization of the single transmembrane helix protein phospholamban [Frank et al. 2000, Li et al. 2001]. The variants of phospholamban showed increased solubility over the wild-type protein and associated into a native-like pentameric

coiled-coil structure. More recently, a computational design procedure was applied to engineer water-soluble variants of the prokaryotic potassium channel KcsA [Slovic et al. 2004]. The resulting analogs were expressed with high yields in *E. coli* and mimicked some of the functional properties of the wild-type channel in aqueous solution, such as oligomerization state and binding of specific channel blocking agents. Very recently, an effort to transform one of GPCRs, mu-opioid receptor, into soluble form has been presented [Perez-Aguilar et al. 2013, Zhao et al. 2014], however, without convincing proof of achieving the goal. In fact, we were unable to reproduce these results based on the published data, i.e. express the water soluble analog of the receptor by expression of the modified gene. Moreover, in neither of these cases the authors were able to crystallize water soluble analogue indicating some structural and/or stability issues of redesigned proteins.

The positive results of successful solubilization strategies and, on the other hand, failure to design water-soluble analogue of more complex protein inspired us to develop new, more robust methods for redesigning the transmembrane domain of GPCRs. This project aims to produce GPCR analogs, which are soluble and stable in water and can be expressed in high quantities. Achieving this goal will help us to understand more deeply the structural features allowing this transformation of membrane to water soluble protein. The importance of generating improved receptor analogs for atomic-resolution biophysical studies, folding, stability investigations and drug design cannot be overstated. The second main goal of the project, a detailed comparison of membrane proteins and their soluble analogs prepared by protein engineering, will also lead to a deeper and more general insight into membrane protein folding and stability, with important consequences for the handling of drug targets.

Although, the ribosome display has been successfully established in our laboratories, every project deals with specific optimizing steps. This was also the case in the GPCR project. Here we mention only two optimization steps related to the DNA construct and the ligation reaction.

Optimization of DNA construct preparation

Since the construct used as a template in *in vitro* transcription must be of the best possible quality, we focused primarily on its preparation. The preparation of the construct for the

selection round involves several steps. In the first step, the library must be amplified with internal primers, then digested and the plasmid digested. The next step is ligation and re-amplification with external primers. Since different primers are used to amplify the NTR library than in the case of off7, in the first step we focused on optimizing the PCR reaction using the internal primers NTR fw and NTR rev.

During the optimization of the individual parameters of the PCR reaction, a certain pattern was observed in the amplification of the mutated library. Repeated amplification reduced the specificity of the reaction and thus the yield of PCR product (Figure 17). By testing the PCR

Figure 17. Test of GPCR library amplification with „desalted“ internal primers. (L) molecular weight marker, (1-4) indication of the number of amplifications.

reaction, we concluded that the differences observed were related to the number of library amplifications. Since the only step between the amplifications was to isolate the DNA from the agarose gel using an extraction kit, we decided to test two different extraction kits, namely the QIAquick® Gel Extraction Kit (250) (Qiagen) and the Monarch® DNA Gel Extraction Kit (NEB). The result of this comparison showed that the extraction kit used did not affect the amplification result.

Based on further tests and theoretical analysis, we decided to focus on the quality of the primers used. For PCR reactions, desalted primers are used as standard, which are sufficient for the basic types of these reactions. However, these primers are a mixture of correctly synthesized oligonucleotides (98%) and oligonucleotides that have been truncated or otherwise damaged in the synthesis process (approximately 2%). It is this contamination that can in some cases cause a reduced yield of the PCR reaction, resp. its complete inhibition. Therefore, we decided to use an amplification primer using ultrapure primers (Figure 18), which were not only desalted after synthesis but also purified by high performance liquid

Figure 18. Test of GPCR library amplification with „HPLC purified“ internal primers.
(L) molecular weight marker, (1-4) indication of the number of amplifications.

chromatography (HPLC) and SDS-PAGE. Comparing the results in Figure 17 and Figure 18, one can see that while the desalting primers significantly reduced the yield of the PCR reaction after the third amplification, we obtained a comparable result after the third amplification using ultra pure primers. With this test, we have thus proved that the quality of the primers used is a decisive parameter in the repeated amplification of a highly diverse library.

Ligation reaction optimization

The ligation process takes place *in vitro* by means of T4 ligase, the efficiency of this reaction being significantly influenced by the plasmid: insert molar ratio. In the case of the GPCR library, a ratio of 1: 7 was used in the first attempt. However, ligation with such a ratio has been shown to be of little efficiency. Although we were able to obtain the desired product, the subsequent PCR reaction with this ligation mixture was quite inefficient. Therefore, we decided to test 4 different plasmid: insert molar ratios, namely 1:1, 1:3, 1:5 and 1:7. The mixture with water, digested pRDV and digested library were heated, before adding the T4 ligation mixture, at 65 °C for 10 minutes. Both the cleaved plasmid and the NTR library can form secondary structures that can prevent hybridization of the cleaved coherent ends. By heating this mixture, the secondary structures are disrupted and thus the ligation efficiency is increased.

The resulting ligated DNA construct is approximately 1400 bp in size (Figure 19). In addition to this product, we observed other bands in the agarose gel that were likely to result from non-specific primer binding to the plasmid. By comparing the individual electrophoretic pathways, one can see that a gradual increase in the amount of insert reduces the non-specificity of the amplification reaction. At the same time, however, we see that the reaction at a ratio of 1:7 was the most specific (absence of any other bands), but also the least efficient

Figure 19. Effect of different plasmid:insert molar ratios on ligation of GPCR library into pRDV. (L) molecular weight marker; (1) control reaction with correctly aligned insert, (2-5) tested plasmid: insert molar ratios- (2) 1:1, (3) 1:3, (4) 1:5, (5) 1:7.

in terms of ligation. Based on this analysis, we found that the optimal plasmid: insert molar ratio for the GPCR library was 1:5.

Besides these two steps, we had to optimize also the step of *in vitro* transcription, which resulted in preparation of our home made buffer leading to higher efficiency of the transcription. Another step that has been optimized was *in vitro* translation, which resulted in preparation of new S30 extract.

After successfully optimizing individual steps of the ribosome display and increasing the diversity of the hKOR library by a combination of random mutation and stag (extended extension process) methods and the subsequent first round of ribosome display (shown in the previous report), we continued in further rounds to completely suppress non-specific binding. The strategy to achieve this goal was to gradually increase the concentration of GdnHCl, specifically at concentrations of 0.25, 0.35 and 0.5 M (Figure 20). We managed to achieve this

Figure 20. (A) First, (B) second and (C) third ribosome display selection round with StEP hKOR library using (A) 0.25 M, (B) 0.35 M and (C) 0.5 M GdnHCl. L-molecular weight marker; 1-2 samples from the well without ligand; 3-4 input mRNA; 5-6 samples from the dynorphin well. Reverse transcription without reverse transcriptase [-] and with reverse transcriptase [+].

goal after several rounds of ribosome display. In addition to suppressing non-specific binding, we also observed a gradual reduction of the PCR product (Figure 20C) after the selection round. This suggests that increasing the number of ribosome display rounds and also increasing the selection pressure using increasing concentrations of GdnHCl is likely to result in selection of hKOR variants that have the desired properties.

After the third and fourth selection rounds, a total of 105 samples of selected hKOR mutants were sent for sequencing. The obtained primary nucleotide sequences were translated into an amino acid sequence using the CLC Genomic Workbench program and compared with each other, resulting in a consensus sequence with prediction of the most common amino acid at a given position. This sequence was then compared to the sequence for native hKOR (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Consensus sequence obtained by the alignment of the hKOR sequences obtained after the third and fourth selection rounds with the sequence of the native hKOR.

The selected variants were sent for DNA sequencing. The first results obtained from DNA sequencing indicated successful selection because:

- (i) most of the selected positions in the original library were mutated (Figure 22),
- (ii) mutations were found at positions not suggested in the original library but located on the surface of hKOR, indicating functionality of the selection pressure to modify amino acid residues on the surface of the protein,
- (iii) one of the positions suggested in the original library, Gly192 in helix 4, was surprisingly not mutated. The analysis revealed steric reasons for the conservatism of this

amino acid, thus pointing to the functionality of the selection pressure to maintain the packed structure of hKOR.

Figure 22. Structure on the left - crystal structure of hKOR with highlighted positions in the original library (**red color**) and positions that were subsequently inserted due to increasing library diversity (**blue color**). Structure on the right - Part of the crystal structure of hKOR with the Gly192 position in helix 4 (**black**) highlighted, which remained unchanged despite its modification in the original library.

Subsequent analysis of the selected sequences by the TANGO method (<http://tango.crg.es/>) led to the confirmation of a reduced tendency of aggregation and thus an increased solubility of selected hKORs by the ribosome display method (Figure 23).

Preliminary analysis of the aggregation state of the proteins thus obtained, in particular the protein designated MC4_H4, the TANGO analysis of which is shown in Figure 23, by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) indicates the existence of this protein in the form of a water-soluble octamer (Figure 24).

These analyzes confirm that our strategy of converting an intra-membrane membrane protein to its water-soluble analogue is fundamentally correct. Using 4 rounds of ribosome display and thanks to suitably adjusted conditions - low denaturant concentrations, which suppressed the non-specific reaction (Figure 20), we were able to select a protein that:

- (1) has a defined secondary structure as determined by circular dichroism measurements,
- (2) has a significantly reduced tendency to aggregate (Figure 24),
- (3) forms a folded 3D structure that, while forming an octamer, is soluble in water in the absence of detergents.

Figure 23. Comparison of TANGO analysis - the tendency to aggregate parts of the primary structure for the original hKOR sequence, the so-called wild type (top of the figure), and the hKOR sequence obtained after ribosome display selection (bottom of the figure). Parts of the molecule that show a tendency of aggregation according to the TANGO method are highlighted on the 3D structures of hKOR.

Figure 24. Chromatographic record of SEC elution of hKOR - MC4_H4 compared with elution of blue dextran and β -amylase molecule. A comparison of the individual elution profiles of the molecules as well as the calibration curve shows that the hKOR selected by us forms octamers.

This achieved result is a great promise for achieving the ultimate goal of the project, which is the transformation of the integral membrane protein by evolutionary techniques into its water-soluble form.

2.3. Enzyme evolution

The quest for biocatalysts endowed with excellent activity, robustness, and novel specificity is continuously increasing. Enzyme discovery and development both depend critically on efficient methods for identifying variants with desirable properties. Nevertheless, nature is an excellent resource for novel biocatalyst, often wild-type enzymes do not fulfill requirements for practical application, they have undesired substrate specificity, poor stability or insufficient catalytic activity. In this respect, protein engineering approaches, especially directed evolution method, have emerged as a tool for improving on nature's catalysts such that they are more suitable as industrial biocatalysts.

Directed evolution combines two independent but powerful technologies: namely, methods for the generation of random genetic libraries and strategies for the selection of variant enzymes that possess specific characteristics. Pioneering work on directed evolution of enzymes is attributed to Arnold [Chen & Arnold 1993] and Stemmer [Stemmer et al. 1994]. Chen and Arnold created subtilisin E, which hydrolysed a peptide substrate 256 times more efficiently than wild-type subtilisin in 60% dimethylformamide by using sequential rounds of random mutagenesis and screening on agar plates. Their work showed, that it is possible to use molecular evolution for tailoring enzyme to unusual environment, since enzyme activity is usually inhibited by organic solvents (e.g. dimethylformamide) used in organic synthesis [Chen & Arnold 1993]. Stemmer and coworkers presented method for *in vitro* homologous recombination, referred as DNA shuffling. The method is based on random fragmentation of parental genes with DNaseI. These fragments are then reassembled into full-length sequences using PCR-like process. After three rounds of DNA shuffling and selection on agar plates was created variant of TEM-1 β -lactamase with greatly improved performance [Stemmer et al. 1994]. Later, Arnold and co-workers, established even more sophisticated shuffling method – staggered extension process (StEP), which yielded an enzyme that had 50 times greater half time at 65 °C compared to wild-type [Zhao et al. 1998].

Initial success of laboratory evolution as engineering tool for enzymes leads to development of numerous additional powerful platforms. Besides, random mutagenesis and DNA shuffling, libraries were generated by numerous additional methods, such as saturation mutagenesis [Wong et al. 2004, Reetz & Carballreira 2007] and diverse recombination based

approaches [Coco et al. 2001, Ostermeier et al. 1999, Xu et al. 2005, Gonzales-Perez et al. 2014]. The creation of sequence space of different possible improved variants was soon easily doable. However, the main bottleneck in engineering studies was and still persists in effective screening of libraries, because many enzymes activities are relatively difficult to screen for in high-throughput manner. The selection and screening strategies employed vary with respect to the selective principle they are based on. The common property of these techniques is linkage of genotype and phenotype. Phenotype means the functional trait (e.i. catalytic activity) and genotype the nucleic acid that can be replicated.

Growth complementation

Selection of engineered enzymes using growth complementation techniques is exclusively conducted in living cells. The examined enzyme property is coupled with the fitness of the host cell in such a way that only the cells containing desired enzyme variants can survive under selective pressure. Cells are transformed with the library followed by plating on selective medium. Selections are therefore limited to engineering detoxifying enzymes (e.g. β -lactamase [Stemmer 1994, Stimple et al. 2019]) or enzymes that synthesize essential nutrients for cell growth and survival [Leemhuis et al. 2009]. For example, enantioselectivity of a lipase was improved through the use of an aspartate auxotrophic E. coli strain. Cell growth was dependent on the hydrolysis of an enantiomeric pure aspartate ester by desirable lipase variants [Boersma et al. 2009]. As this selection strategy also selected for nonenantioselective lipases, a suicide inhibitor of the opposite enantiomer was used to inactivate lipases with activity toward the “incorrect” enantiomer, thus, inhibiting cell growth. Similar selection strategy has been reported where lipase catalyzed hydrolysis of the “wrong” enantiomer yields a poison (fluoroacetic acid), whereas hydrolysis of the desirable enantiomer yields a carbon source (acetate) [Reetz et al. 2008]. Thus only cells expressing a lipase of desirable enantioselectivity can grow [Leemhuis et al. 2009].

Agar plate screening

Agar plate screening is the simplest format, which enable enzyme variants and metagenomic libraries to be screened. The crucial factor with this screening technique is that substrate conversion creates a visual signal, such as fluorescence or color, to identify colonies expressing an enzyme with desirable properties [Leemhuis et al. 2009, van Rossum et al.

2013]. This approach was successfully used in screening for the conversion of a β -galactosidase into a β -fucosidase. *E. coli* transformants (~1,000 per plate) were absorbed to filter paper and then incubated with 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indoyl- β -D-fucopyranoside resulting in color development by colonies expressing β -fucosidase activity. A screening approach for glycosynthases was recently described which detects the release of hydrofluoric acid, the by-product of the glycosynthase reaction, via the pH indicator methyl red [Ben-David & Shoham 2008]. *E. coli* colonies (~600) were pressed onto filter paper, lysed with liquid nitrogen, and then soaked in a substrate solution with methyl red. Colonies that turned red the quickest were selected, yielding a variant with 35-fold higher kcat Van Loo et al. devised a screening system whereby epoxide hydrolase activity could be visualized on agar plates. Agar plates were incubated with epoxybutane vapor which was converted to the corresponding diol by functional epoxide hydrolase variants [van Loo et al. 2004]. *E. coli* oxidized the diol forming excess NADH which led to safranin O uptake, coloring colonies expressing active epoxide hydrolases. In general, agar plate screenings are easy to operate and straightforward to identify active variants. However, low dynamic ranges of these screening approaches generally do not allow for accurately distinguishing differences in catalytic rates. Besides, only libraries of up to ~ 10⁵ can be screened [Leemhuis et al. 2009, Dietrich et al. 2010]. In general, agar plate screening has successfully been employed to screen for multiple enzyme classes such as cellulases, lipase/esterase, proteases, laccases and oxidoreductases [Kennedy et al. 2011, van Rossum et al. 2013].

Mitrotiter plates

The most commonly applied screening strategy for enzymes is based on microtiter plates. Although higher density formats, e.g. 1536 and 9600-well, are commercially available, the 96-well plate is the most widely used format. Traditional enzyme activity assays can be performed in a microtiter plate by adding reaction components and either cells, crude cell extracts or purified proteins manually [Xiao et al. 2014]. Among the most convenient microtiter plate/based enzyme activity assay are colorimetric or fluorometric assays [Chang et al. 1999, Wang et al. 2014]. For certain enzymatic reactions, the disappearance of substrates or formations of products can be easily identified by macroscopic observation or measuring UV-vis absorbance or fluorescence using a plate reader. Since these assays highly

depend on the chemistry and availability of native substrates, they are not generally applicable [Xiao et al. 2014]. The screening capacity is between 102-104 library members.

2.3.1. The case of haloalkane dehalogenase

Successful establishment of ribosome display in our laboratory has motivated us to widen its application in protein engineering of enzymes. We aimed to enhance biophysical and biochemical properties of the group of hydrolases, named haloalkane dehalogenases (HLDs). HLDs catalyse the hydrolytic cleavage of the carbon-halogen bond in diverse halogenated aliphatic hydrocarbons [Janssen 2004]. Substrates of HLDs include also common environmental pollutants, such as 1,2-dichloroethane or 1,2,3-trichloropropane [Damborsky et al. 2001].

HLDs belong to an α/β hydrolases superfamily. Tertiary protein structure is composed of two different domains: (i) conserved α/β hydrolase domain, which is formed by eight centrally located β -sheets surrounded by two α helices and (ii) helical, so-called, cap domain [Janssen 2004]. Most structural differences between HLDs are in the cap domain. The enzyme active site is deeply buried between two domains and it is formed by a catalytic pentad consisting of a nucleophile (Asp), a base (His), a catalytic acid (Asp/Glu) and two aminoacid residues for halide ion stabilization (Trp-Trp/Trp-Asn).

The dehalogenation reaction is realized through two sequential steps. First, the S_N2 nucleophilic substitution mechanism replaces the halogen to form a covalent intermediate ester. In the second step, after the addition of the water molecules, the halide ion, the proton and the corresponding alcohol are released [Verschuere et al. 1993]. The hydrolytic reaction turns halogenated alkanes to the non-hazardous alcohols.

HLDs mediated dehalogenation has a high application potential in various fields. They are used to remove toxic environmental pollutants, for decontamination of chemical warfare agents, in biomonitoring of environmental pollutants, protein labeling and chemical synthesis of substances. The discovery of high enantioselectivity of HLDs has made them attractive for a pharmaceutical industry [Koudelakova et al. 2013]. HLDs serve also as model enzymes for

studying structure–function relationships of more than 100 000 members of the α/β hydrolase superfamily and in development of rational protein design [Chovancova et al. 2012]. Recently, HLDs have become an interesting model for exploring the role of protein dynamics, hydration [Amaro et al. 2015] and molecular gating [Gora et al. 2013].

Very important functional characteristics of HLDs include their robustness and broad substrate specificity. HLDs catalyze the hydrolysis of chlorinated, brominated, and iodinated alkanes, alkenes, cycloalkanes, alcohols, carboxylic acids, esters, ethers, epoxides, amides and nitriles [Damborsky et al. 2001, Koudelakova et al. 2011]. Substrate specificity of HLDs is the result of unique structure and properties of the cap domain, the active site, and the access tunnels [Koudelakova et al. 2011]. Structural composition of the cap domain in the individual HLD member determines shape and volume of the active site and at the same time it shapes the enzyme tunnel, which connects the active site with the surrounding environment. Nevertheless, a wide range of potential practical applications of HLDs has many limitations. Wild-type enzymes usually perform low catalytic activity toward desirable or noncognate substrates, enzyme stability and affinity is often insufficient and catalytic reaction runs under narrow physico-chemical conditions [Koudelakova et al. 2013]. Biotechnological processes often take place under harsh conditions (elevated temperature, extreme pH levels, presence of organic solvents etc.) compared to physiological environment. Therefore, there is a significant gap between properties of natural enzymes and biocatalysts specifically required for industrial processes [Turner 2009]. To widen HLDs applications as industrial biocatalyst, properties of naturally occurring enzymes needs to be optimized.

The chief characteristics of HLDs are stability and catalytic efficiency, thus there is a strong demand especially for stable and catalytically efficient HLDs enzymes. Engineering both, stability and at the same time catalytic efficiency is profoundly complex given to forces and factors which influence them. In addition, because of existing trade-off between stability and protein function, in a pursuit of enhancing one property, the second one could be diminished [Siddiqui 2017, Romero & Arnold 2009]. To reach such complex alteration of enzyme, several amino acids substitutions must be introduced into protein structure. Two distinct ways to engineer proteins have appeared during the last few decades: rational design and directed evolution. Introduction of several parallel functional mutations by rational design

is still very challenging. On the contrary, it is feasible by directed evolution and such approach has proven to be considerably powerful in modifying specific protein/enzyme characteristics [Turner 2009, Romero & Arnold 2009]. HLDs are valuable biocatalysts with immense practical application, however, their widespread utilization is still hindered by many limitations. The most critical obstacles are their insufficient stability and catalytic activity. By now, properties of HLDs (substrate specificity, enantioselectivity, activity) have been predominantly modified by engineering their tunnels, connecting bulk solvent with the active site [Pavlova et al. 2009, Liskova et al. 2015, Marek et al. 2020]. This strategy has proved to be appropriate; however, we are still not able to construct HLDs with qualities satisfying biotechnological requirements. Rather than focusing an attention on altering the HLDs tunnel by rational design, we propose to use method of directed evolution, i.e. introducing “blind” (random) mutations in combination with highly efficient ribosome display selection. The goal of this project is to provide „proof of principle“ for possible usage of HaloTag technology in combination with the protein evolution method - ribosome display - for modification of catalytic properties of selected enzyme group - haloalkane dehalogenases. This ambitious goal relies on utilization of a method for directed evolution of protein – ribosome display. The ribosome display is especially powerful method in complex protein engineering project such as ours in which we aim to increase catalytic efficiency of selected enzymes for specific substrate(s) without compromising their stabilities. Successful accomplishment of this goal will provide us with information and tools for analogous modification of catalytic properties also in other enzyme families with immense potential for biotechnological application.

As a model HLDs for ribosome display method has been chosen DhaA enzyme variant originating from bacterial strain *Rhodococcus* [Newman et al. 1999]. DhaA is well studied and there are available a lot of information about its structure and mechanism of action. DhaA has been intensively analyzed, mainly because of its dehalogenation activity toward the anthropogenic compound TCP, which is notorious as a toxic and recalcitrant industrial by-product [Bosma et al. 2002, Gray et al. 2003].

First, HLD gene were transformed into proper format. The genes encoded HLDs were cloned into plasmid pRDV specific to the needs of RD. The stop codon was omitted from all

genes to ensure forming of ternary complexes after in vitro translation. The optimal conditions for PCR and ligation reaction were also adjusted.

Figure 25. Schematic illustration of ribosome display method. The gene encoding protein of interest is mutated and created DNA library is expressed in vitro. Since mRNAs do not have stop codons, after translation ribosomes stall at the end of mRNAs and proteins stay captured in form of ternary complexes (mRNA-ribosome-protein). These complexes are then selected in microtiter well against suitable ligand. Unbound complexes are washed away and from tightly bound complexes mRNA is eluted, which is reverse transcribed, amplified and serves as the template for next round.

Having prepared genetic construct, we focused on selection/panning step. This step is critical, because it directs selection pressure. Selection step also requires immobilization of ligand, which could be an issue especially for enzymes. The wealth of knowledge on DhaA and other HLDs led us to so-called HaloTag technology [Los et al. 2008]. The technology is based on irreversible covalent binding of miscellaneous labeled ligands by the mutant DhaA (HaloTag protein) which forms a genetically encoded fusion with a target protein. The covalent binding of a chlorinated ligand is enabled by the mutation of the catalytic base histidine to phenylalanine, which impairs the final hydrolysis step and leads to irreversible trapping of the alkylenzyme intermediate. The synthetic ligands consist of a chloroalkane linker attached to various fluorescent dyes, affinity handles or solid surfaces [Los et al. 2008, Encell et al. 2012].

Underlying principle of Halotag technology (replacement of histidine, and affinity tag) was suggested for capturing of HLDs in microtiter well. To test this idea, we conducted two independent preliminary rounds of ribosome display against biotinylated haloalkane (Figures 25, 26). For testing a feasibility of this approach we used DhaA-Halotag variant of HLDs, primarily due to strong binding affinity toward chosen substrate. The presence of the band in the lane 6 (and absence of a band in the lane 2) (Figure 26), demonstrated successful selection round of ribosome display and at the same time, the feasibility to capture HLD on the surface of the microtiter wells in the form of ternary complexes. However, bands in control wells 1,3,5 (Figure 26A) indicate the presence of unspecific binding and contamination with DNA. By using DNase treatment after panning step this unspecific binding has been suppressed (Figure 26B). These preliminary rounds also showed that selected fraction of HLD is quite low, represented by very weak band in the lanes 6 (Figure 26). We suspected, that short variant of biotinylated chloroalkane that we used in these experiments might lead to such low yield of selection. Therefore, longer PEG-ylated substrate (ligand) has been used in the next binding experiments.

Figure 26. 2 Preliminary rounds of ribosome display with DhaA Halotag variant against HaloTag Biotin Ligand. L- 100 bp DNA ladder, 1,3,5 – negative controls, 1 and 2 – sample from the well without the substrate, 2 and 3 – reverse transcribed mRNA after in vitro transcription, 4 and 5 – sample from the well with the substrate. Reverse transcription without reverse transcriptase [-], reverse transcription with reverse transcriptase [+].

Next, the DNA library was prepared. There are several available strategies to generate directed evolution libraries ranging from (simple) point mutagenesis through gene recombination or shuffling, to different computational tools set to designing DNA/protein libraries. Genes encoded dehalogenases (gift from prof. Damborsky) do not share adequate sequence identity, we could not prepare the DNA library by gene shuffling. Instead, we decided to randomize DhaA gene by error-prone PCR method using three different

concentrations of mutagenic nucleotides 8-oxo-dGTP and dPTP. Resulted libraries were analyzed from the aspect of frequency of induced mutations (Table 1). The libraries prepared with 3 and 5 μM concentration of nucleotide analogues were mixed together. As a result,

Table 1. Summary of prepared libraries and induced mutations.

Concentration of 8-oxo-dGTP a dPTP	3 μM	5 μM	10 μM
Nonsynonymous mutations	85%	86%	78%
Synonymous (silent) mutations	15%	14%	22%
Transversions	15%	14%	13%
Transitions	85%	86%	87%
Mutational frequency on average	2.8 mu./gene	7.1 mu./gene	6.8 mu./gene

initial library of DhaA variants with optimized mutational frequency, in average with 5 mutations per gene, was created, cloned into pRDV plasmid and selected by ribosome display (Figure 27). We note that, first and second round were still performed with shorter substrate and third round with PEG-Biotin-Ligand, longer substrate. As it turned out, longer substrate variant enhanced specific binding of dehalogenases variants, but unspecific binding in the control well without target (Figure 27, lane 2) also increased. After third round of ribosome display, there was noticeable enrichment towards selected fraction of DhaA in lane 6 compared to the selected fraction in the lane 2 (Figure 27, 3rd round). Obtained enrichment is evident when one compares lanes 6 in the third vs the first round. This indicates selection process favoring specifically bound HLDs. We decided to explore the resulted library fraction in more detail and sent few samples for sequencing.

Figure 27. Selection rounds of ribosome display with prepared DhaA library against PEG-ylated Halotag Biotin Ligand. L- 100 bp DNA ladder, 1,3,5 – negative controls, 1 and 2 – sample from the well without the substrate, 2 and 3 – reverse transcribed mRNA after in vitro transcription, 4 and 5 –sample from the well with the substrate. Reverse transcription without reverse transcriptase [-], reverse transcription with reverse transcriptase [+].

Following sequence analysis showed that individual selected mutants after third round of ribosome display contain different point mutations. We noticed two hot spot positions: (i) position 102, where leucin was mutated to glutamine and in one case to prolin and (ii) position 124, where lysin was mutated to glutamic acid or asparagine (Figure 28). Surprisingly, as the third „hot-spot“ was identified extensive deletion of 13 aminoacids at position 132-144 in 4 out 10 mutants (two of these mutants besides other mutations, contain also frame shift mutation and later were excluded from analysis). Such mutation is generally very rare, but in case of HLDs, it may not be entirely coincidence, once the position of this mutation is examined. The deletion was identified as a part of loop 9 in N-terminal part of cap domain, situated near enzyme slot tunnel (Figure 28). Phylogenetic analysis of the HLDs family has shown that the N-terminal part of the cap domain is one of the most variable regions within the whole family as well as individual subfamilies HLD-I, HLD-II and HLD-III [Chovancova et al. 2007]. The deletion site contains amino acid residues that participate in the formation of the access tunnel cavity. HLDs tunnels are considered to be sites of molecular evolution and substrate specificity of HLDs [Chovancova et al. 2007, Pries et al. 1994]. Modification of access tunnels has also been shown to be an effective strategy in modulating the catalytic activity of

Figure 28. Sequence based alignment after third round of ribosome display with DhaA library and highlighted identified hot spots (orange arrows) and deletion (magenta box). Structure of DhaA: cap domain is blue, alpha/beta hydrolase fold domain in green, hot spots in orange and deletion in magenta color.

HLDs [Chaloupkova et al., 2003, Pavlova et al. 2009], but also of other enzymes [Zamocky et al. 1995, Qian et al. 2009]. Modulation of the permeability of these tunnels (narrowing and widening of the tunnel diameter by amino acid exchange) is also associated with increased/decreased stability of HLDs [Liskova et al. 2015, Markova et al. 2020]. The identification of this deletion is the first indication that the selection process might work. The sequences originate from two rounds of RD with short ligands, therefore selection pressure selected those enzymes, that had better access to the active site, e.g. enzymes with deletion.

Figure 29. Selection rounds of ribosome display with haloalkane dehalogenases linB (A) and dbeA (B). L-100 bp DNA ladder, 1,3,5 – negative controls, 1 and 2 – sample from the well without the substrate, 2 and 3 – reverse transcribed mRNA after in vitro transcription, 4 and 5 –sample from the well with the substrate. Reverse transcription without reverse transcriptase [-], reverse transcription with reverse transcriptase [+].

Preliminary results obtained from ribosome display of DhaA library motivated us to apply similar approach to other dehalogenase genes for evolution-directed selection. We performed ribosome display with **LinB** and **dbeA** dehalogenase to compare them along with DhaA case. However, ribosome displays with both dehalogenases were unsuccessful. In case of **LinB**, there was no visible selected fraction (no visible band in the line 6) (Figure 29), while for **dbeA** was observed strong unspecific binding (density of a band in the line 2 is higher than in the line 6) (Figure 29).

After all the above experiments, we returned to engineering of DhaA Halotag variant, which we used in the first testing round (Figure 26). The library for this variant was prepared as described above. Overall, we reached fifth round of ribosome display with Halotag variant. Despite many modifications/optimizations, it was almost impossible to completely suppress an unspecific binding (band in the line 2). At the beginning, after first round was observed equal fraction of the selected proteins in the well with and without substrate (Figure 30, 1st round, lane 6 vs 2). Later, in the second round, unspecific binding was partially suppressed,

Figure 30. Selection rounds of ribosome display with DhaA_Halotag library. First-fourth round: L- 100 bp DNA ladder, 1,3,5,7,9 – negative controls, 1,2,5,6 – sample from the well without the substrate 3,4,7,8 –sample from the well with the substrate, 9,10 – reverse transcribed mRNA after in vitro transcription. Fourth round: 1-4 washing with 3 M urea, 5-8 washing with 4 M urea. B. Ribosome display with DhaA_Halotag library including different concentration of guanidine hydrochlorid and urea within washing step. L – 100 bp DNA ladder. 1-14 samples from the well without target, 15-16 mRNA reverse transcribed after in vitro transcription. 1,3,5,7,9,11,13,15- negative controls. Reverse transcription without reverse transcriptase [-], reverse transcription with reverse transcriptase [+].

primarily thank to short incubations with 0.5 M guanidine hydrochlorid (GdnHCl) and at the same time, the enrichment was achieved (Figure 30, 2nd round, lane 6 vs 2). Longer incubations with GdnHCl did not improve selection, rather the enrichment was lost again (data not shown). Thereafter, the influence of different concentration of GdnHCl and urea was tested in the washing step (Figure 30B). The most effective result was achieved with 3 M urea (2x5

min). Then third and fourth round of RD was conducted with this optimization (Figure 30, 3rd and 4th round). During fourth round, washing step was also managed with even higher concentration of urea, 4 M. This urea concentration was shown to be high and likely led to dissociation of ribosomes (Figure 30, 4th round, lane 8). The last, fifth round, did not bring further refinement, therefore libraries selected after third and fourth round were subjected to investigation.

In addition, we note that during selection rounds we tried also option called prepanning. Firstly, the whole translation reaction (ternary complexes) is put into additional prepanning „well without the ligand“ and right after short incubation (3 min) ternary complexes are placed to panning wells (the purpose of this option is to remove strong unspecific binders and aggregates before panning).

To sum up, 16 sequences of Halotag variants after third round and 20 sequences of Halotag variants after four round were aligned. Independently from the sequence analysis of DhaA, this sequence alignment showed position 102 as a hot spot again, mostly within variants from fourth round. This mutation is located at the center of the α/β hydrolase domain structure in the $\beta 6$ sheet. β sheets located in the center of this domain are highly conserved in HLDs [Chovancova et al. 2007], we hypothesized, that this mutation could be interesting in terms of enzyme function or stability. Another identified hot spot include position 15 and 97, where glutamic acid was mutated to glycine or lysin, position 103 where valine was

Figure 31. Examples of selected mutants based on sequence alignment. Three dimensional structure of DhaA (1CQW) in grey, catalytic pentad in magenta and position of identified mutations in blue. A. mutations inside the structure, B. mutations on surface, C. mutations on surface and inside of the enzyme structure.

mutated alanine. In general, mutation positions can be formally divided into 3 groups (representative examples of the enzymes are shown in Figure 31): (i) inside the protein (Figure 31A), (ii) on the protein surface (Figure 31B), (iii) dispersed within the protein structure (Figure 31C). Similarly, to the examples of enzyme engineering studies, hot spot sites have been located distant from active site, where they can affect enzyme function through long-range interactions [Fasan et al. 2008, Shimotohno et al. 2001]. Identification of these mutations was another indication, that selection process *via* ribosome display is working.

Possible improvement of the selected mutants has to be confirmed by the study of their biophysical and biochemical properties. In order to study protein properties, protein/mutants are produced in suitable expression system (ideally with high yield) and purified. Indispensable prerequisite for these requirements is the solubility of the protein. The selection process/panning step in ribosome display stands on the assumption that only properly folded proteins have ability for ligand binding. Therefore, mutants selected by ribosome display, in theory, should be also soluble. On the other site, *in vitro* conditions compare to the cell environment, do not have any control quality mechanism for produced proteins, which means, soluble proteins and insoluble aggregates are present in mixture used for selection. Insoluble fraction of proteins could be present also in selected libraries, especially in our case, as we experienced difficulties with unspecific binding (see above). To speed up manufacture of testing the suitability of selected mutants, an easy-to-handle

Figure 32. Figure 8 Test solubility of selected mutants selected by ribosome display. The desired protein was present at 33kDa. L - low molecular weight marker S – supernatant of lysed cells, P- pellet of lysed cells. 1-8: selected mutants of HLDs, band corresponding to the size of DhaA - red arrows.

solubility assay for proteins has been established. In this test, proteins are heterologously produced, lysed with commercial extraction reagent and centrifuged using high speed (usually around 20 000g). Soluble part containing also soluble proteins is supernatant and insoluble part together with cell debris is pelleted. However, based on this assay, all of our mutants were found in pellet, insoluble part (Figure 32). The main disadvantage of this assay is that could result in false negatives. We suspected, that also inappropriate expression conditions were used. To address the problem with solubility and expression, wildtype DhaA introduced in three different types of plasmids was tested by solubility assay. The purpose of using these plasmids was to examine effect of different promoters, since promoters are central elements that affects the strength and duration of transcription [Correa and Oppedo 2011]. Namely, T5 promotor (pQE plasmid), tac promotor (pAQN plasmid) and T7 promotor (pET plasmid) were used. In addition, expressions were performed in two distinct type of *E. coli* cells, XL1Blue and BL21(DE3) (Figure 33). The selection of the *E. coli* strain can have profound effect on the

Figure 33. SDS-PAGE profile of solubility test of wildtype DhaA. The desired protein was present at 33kDa. L- low molecular weight marker 1- pellet of lysed XL1Blue, pQE plasmid 2- supernatant of lysed XL1Blue, pQE plasmid 3 - pellet of lysed BL21, pQE plasmid 4 - supernatant of lysed BL21, pQE plasmid 5 - pelet of lysed XL1blue, pAQN plasmid 6 - supernatant of lysed XL1Blue, pAQN plasmid 7 - pellet of lysed BL21, pAQN plasmid 8 – supernatant of lysed BL21, pAQN plasmid 9 - pellet of lysed XL1Blue, pET plasmid 10 - supernatant of lysed XL1Blue, pET plasmid 11 – pellet of lysed BL21, pET plasmid 12 - supernatant of lysed BL21, pET plasmid 13 - pellet of lysed cells, 3C protease 14 - supernatant of lysed cells, 3C protease.

recombinant production since it gives the genetic background in which protein synthesis occurs. Fundamental difference between XL1Blue and BL21 lies in the absence of proteases in BL21 strain, thus reducing the degradation of the target protein. BL21(DE3) derivative also contains a chromosomal copy of the T7 RNA polymerase under the control of the lacUV promoter, which is primarily suitable for expression of recombinant protein under the control of the T7 promoter [Correa and Oppizzo 2011]. Obtained results showed, that even wildtype DhaA, that is otherwise soluble were identified as a part of insoluble pellet (Figure 33, lane 1) as well as additional soluble protein (3C protease), that was used as control too (Figure 33, lane 13). In some cases, we were not able to identify if the protein was even produced (e.g. Figure 33, lanes 3, 4). The positive outcome of this test was, that combination of XL1Blue transformed with pQE plasmid carrying wildtype DhaA leads to the best expression level (Figure 33, lane 1, red arrow). After this optimization we decided to scale up expression volume and repeat the expression in both bacterial hosts again (Figure 34). Moreover, two

Figure 34. SDS-PAGE profile of purification of DhaA expressed at 25 °C and 37 °C. The desired protein was present at 33kDa. A-B Purification of DhaA in XL1Blue cells. C-D: Purification of DhaA in BL21 cells. L- low molecular weight marker 1- pellet of lysed cells 2 – supernatant of lysed 3- flowthrough 4 – elution fraction of 500 mM imidazole.

different induction temperatures (25°C and 37 °C) for production of protein were used, since only induction at 37°C were used in previous experiments. Induction temperature is important parameter that can effect protein solubility. It was shown that lower temperatures during induction (16-25 °C) can increase the final yield of soluble protein. It was assumed that a slower translation rate could favor the correct folding of the protein [Vera et al. 2007]. Obtained results indicated that in all cases the reached expression level was quite high, but BL21 strain was shown to be better option for soluble expression. After lysis and centrifugation of BL21 with expressed DhaA, protein was present in supernatant fraction and also successfully purified by affinity chromatography. In addition, both induction temperatures were found to be suitable. Large scale production of DhaA helped us to finally find optimal conditions for soluble expression of wildtype DhaA. These conditions were used in following experiments. Since solubility assay did not proved to be reliable regarding to rapid screening of HLDs mutants, we will put much effort into the large scale expression and purification of the most interesting mutants – mutants with deletion.

As an alternative to screening solubility of proteins, direct screening for protein function, in our case, catalytic activity, would be more convenient. A pH indicator dye-based colorimetric assay [Chang et al. 1999] was established in our laboratory. The assay is based on

Figure 35. Test of *in vivo* pH assay. A. mixture of cells (BL21+ wtDhaA or BL21) after addition of bromothymolblue indicator dye. B. mixture of cells (BL21+ wtDhaA or BL21) 15 min after addition of 1-chlorobutane. Negative control, without substrate [NC], reaction mixture with substrate [+].

a decrease in the pH of a weakly-buffered medium when protons and chloride ions are released by the enzyme. As a reaction proceed, colour of indicator dye (bromothymolblue) incorporated in buffer medium is changing. This assay is used to monitor dehalogenation reactions in the cells, without need for cell lysis. At the beginning, performance of this assay was optimized for wildtype form of DhaA enzyme. As a substrate was used 1-chlorobutane, which is structurally similar to reactive linker of Halotag-Biotin ligand used for ribosome display. The colour change from green to yellow was monitored with cells containing active DhaA. For comparison, the dehalogenation reaction was monitored in cells, which do not contain any dehalogenase gene (Figure 35). After 15 min, reaction mixture in tube with DhaA and added substrate changed to yellow. This indicated that DhaA catalysed dehalogenation of chloride ions from substrate and protons produced as a result of enzyme activity lowered pH of the reaction mixture (Figure 35B). Supportive data were obtained by measurement of UV-vis absorption spectra of reaction mixture with DhaA 15 min after addition of substrate. This analysis included following controls: reaction mixture containing only BL21 cells, BL21 cells with expressed inactive DhaAH272F or different enzyme (3C protease) (Figure 36). Since for

Figure 36. UV-Vis absorption spectra of bromothymol blue/Tris solution 15 min after addition of 1-chlorobutane. Prior measurement cells were pelleted and only supernatant was used for measurement. A. BL21 cells with expressed active DhaA + substrate B. BL21 cells with expressed inactive DhaAH272F + substrate -pink line C. BL21 cells with expressed 3C protease D. BL21 cells NC -corresponding negative control without substrate.

monitoring of dehalogenation are used whole cells, these control reactions assisted to link change of pH to DhaA activity and not to spontaneous change of pH owing to cellular metabolism. Obtained absorption spectra have two obvious properties. One is the absorption peak centered around 400-440 nm, which is pH dependent and red-shifts when pH is changing. Another feature is the fixed absorption peak centered at 616 nm and its intensity decreases gradually when solution turns acidic. The significant change of absorption spectra was observed only with cells containing active DhaA (Figure 36A). Compare to other controls, there is an obvious shift of the peak to around 429 nm, as well as the intensity of peak at 616 nm was significantly decreased. Our data showed, that this assay can be adopted to measuring DhaA activity in vivo using only cell culture. The same experimental set up will be used for other HLDs mutants and compared with wild-type form. This assay can be easily modified into a microtiter plate format as well as agar plates for high-throughput screening. Before rapid screening of selected libraries, reverse mutation of catalytic histidine into the active site have to be introduced to ensure mutant HLDs will be able to complete dehalogenation reaction through both steps. Libraries with mentioned mutations will be screened in agar plates or microtiter plates. Mutants with improved catalytic activity observed with colorimetric assay will be further examined in detail.

3. YEAST DISPLAY

One of the specific goal of the CasProt project is firm establishing of protein evolution methods such as ribosome display and yeast display in the laboratory CIB TIP-UPJS. The results presented in the above parts of this report clearly demonstrate that the ribosome display was firmly established in the laboratories CIB. On the other hand, the method of the yeast display has not been yet introduced in our laboratories. The main reason of that is the absence of FACS sorter, an inevitable instrument for establishing the method of the yeast display. Fortunately, very recently we obtained the project with the aim of developing flexible protein platforms by evolutionary techniques for the detection of viral particles - the project BioPickmol (Development of nanosensory photonic systems for rapid virus detection using methods of controlled evolution of protein platforms: the case of SARS-CoV-2). Within this project, we planned to purchase FACS sorter, which is in fact in the process of the procurement. As the result of this situation, in the next part of the report we will present an overview of the yeast display.

Surface display represents an emerging and innovative technology by which genes (genotype) linked to the displayed protein variants (phenotype) can be easily traced. Phage display was the first technique developed [Smith 1985] and is still the most commonly used method to evolve proteins. Two other major display formats include yeast [Boder & Wittrup 1997] and ribosome [Hanes & Plückthun 1997] display, but many other cellular and acellular approaches exist. Additional high-throughput combinatorial library screening platforms encompass *in vitro* compartmentalization (IVC), mRNA, aptamers, cis-activity based (CIS) and covalent antibody display (CAD) [Galán et al. 2016] or mammalian cell display [Beerli et al. 2008].

Yeast surface display (YSD) is an *in vivo* method developed by Wittrup and Boder for screening of rare functional binders [Boder & Wittrup 1997]. Since the first introduction of the technology in 1997, it has become a useful engineering tool for a broad spectrum of biotechnology, biomedical and industrial application. In YSD method, each yeast contains genetically encoded protein variant fused to a cell surface anchor protein. Variants are expressed, and the protein of interest is displayed on the yeast cell surface where it is

accessible for soluble ligands. Afterwards, cells are mixed with labelled target molecule. In phage and ribosome display, selection from libraries is generally based on a capture and elution procedure, but since yeast-displayed protein variants are flanked by fluorescently labelled epitope tags, selections from cell displayed libraries are typically performed using fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS). Selected protein variants are then identified by sequencing the corresponding genetic material recovered from the cells.

YSD technique was first developed for affinity maturation of existing proteins (Figure 37), but later it showed its effectiveness in isolation of new molecules from naive combinatorial libraries of multiple antibodies and nonimmunoglobulin scaffolds [Angelini et al. 2015, Cherf & Cochran 2015]. Subsequently, the method found another usage and it has been successfully exploited to enhance protein stability and enzymatic activity, in epitope mapping and to improve the recombinant production [Cherf & Cochran 2015]. YSD has been employed to engineer a plethora of secreted proteins, extracellular membrane domains [Zhao et al. 2014] as well as some membrane protein [Bacon et al. 2019].

The major advantage of YSD over other display techniques is eucaryotic expression system and compatibility with the flow cytometry. The overall scheme of protein synthesis is similar in all living cells, however, compared to bacteria, the range of folded polypeptides in the eukaryotic cytosol is more complex. To handle variety of conformational requirements in eucaryotic cells, more sophisticated folding system is needed [Young et al. 2004]. Plus, many newly synthesized proteins are post-translationally modified and although posttranslational protein modifications occur also in procaryotes they are considerably different from those in eukaryotes [Macek et al. 2019]. YSD mimics the protein processing machinery of mammalian cells. It includes foldases and chaperones present in the endoplasmic reticulum that are essential for efficient assembly of three-dimensional protein structure and thus allowing presentation of sequence variants less accessible to procaryotic hosts [Boder & Wittrup 1997].

YSD offers several further benefits, compared to other display formats, but also contains some drawbacks. As already mentioned, fused proteins contain epitope tags (c-myc and HA tag) compatible with flow cytometric analysis [VanAntwerp & Wittrup 2000]. Since these tags are allocated on the C- and N- terminus of the target protein, upon their

Figure 37. Isolating high-affinity protein variants from a yeast-displayed library by FACS.

Following transformation of yeast cells with a gene library and induction of surface expression, two main strategies are used to differentially label the displayed library prior to screening: (1) an equilibrium binding strategy where the library is incubated with a ligand concentration 5–10 times greater than the expected K_d value of the highest affinity variant, resulting in near saturation of tight binding variants and partial labeling of weaker affinity variants at equilibrium, and (2) a kinetic binding strategy where the library is incubated with ligand as described for the equilibrium binding strategy, but unbound ligand is removed by washing and the library is then incubated either with a 100-fold excess of unlabeled ligand or in a sufficiently large volume of buffer to prevent rebinding of dissociated ligand. During this second incubation step, the excess unlabeled ligand or large incubation volume prevents dissociated labeled ligands from rebinding. Proteins are thus differentiated based on their dissociation rate constants (k_{off}), with variants having the slowest k_{off} retaining the largest percentage of prebound labeled ligand. Addition of a fluorescently labeled anti-epitope tag antibody (not shown) permits normalization of yeast surface expression levels with binding, allowing the highest affinity variants to be isolated by FACS. Sorted pools of yeast clones can be expanded in culture for either analysis or a subsequent round of sorting, or DNA from these clones can be isolated, subjected to mutagenesis, and used to transform a new batch of yeast for further directed protein evolution [Cherf & Cochran 2015].

immunofluorescence staining, full-length protein expression can be verified using a flow cytometer (Figure 38). In comparison with other techniques, this offers an additional quality control check during the variants isolation [Doerner et al. 2014]. FACS sorting also enables to visualize both the targeted and non-targeted populations during the selection and the stringency of selection can easily be varied [Bowley et al. 2007]. The system is able to sample a variant library considerably more fully than phage [Bowley et al. 2007]. YSD has relatively

low technical and time requirements compared to other eucaryotic display systems. Low cost of culturing microorganisms, the potential high yield and the low contamination risk are some benefits over mammalian expression systems [Gai & Wittrup 2007]. Disadvantages include smaller mutant library sizes compared to optional methods, differential glycosylation in yeast compared to mammalian cells and the technique is hampered by the low flow rate of the majority of flow cytometry instruments currently available [Linciano et al. 2019].

Figure 38. (A) Representative picture of a fluorescently stained cells with an anti-HA and anti-Myc antibodies. (B) Dual colour fluorescence density plot. FACS analysis indicates that 72% of individual cells have both green and red fluorescence staining on their surfaces [Wang et al. 2010].

First step in the search for a new protein variant relies on a generation of genetic variants libraries. Nowadays, there are three common diversification strategies that can be employed in library creation, in particular, random mutagenesis, focused mutagenesis and recombination [Bratulic & Badran 2017]. Rapid development of research techniques brings up new possibilities and recently, CRISPR/Cas9 editing technology was used to diversify targeted stretches of a protein of interest in situ [Erdogan et al. 2020, Oh et al. 2020]. CRISPR-Cas9 systems thus opened completely new possibilities for advancing the protein engineering.

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (*S. cerevisiae*) is the most used yeast for cell surface display, but other hosts such as *Pichia pastoris* or *Yarrowia lipolytica* are also utilized. Yeasts offer a multiple choice of cell anchoring protein – Aga1p, Aga2p, Cwp1p, Cwp2p, Tip1p, Flo1p, Sed1p, YCR89w, and Tir1 [Cherf & Cochran 2015]. Choosing proper anchor protein is an important decision, because it can impact the total amount of protein expression and display [Tanaka et al. 2012]. An appropriate anchor protein should contain a signal sequence that will enable

efficient transport to the cell surface, rigid immobilization of the target protein on the cell surface, and should not hamper with the stability or activity of the displayed protein [Tanaka & Kondo 2015]. The most frequently used yeast display system is the one developed by Boder and Wittrup [Boder & Wittrup 1997] in which protein of interest is fused to the Aga2p adhesion subunit of the *S. cerevisiae* α -agglutinin mating protein (Figure 39). The Aga2p subunit in turn is by disulfide bonds linked to the cell wall associated Aga1 anchoring subunit, connecting the protein of interest to the cell wall. Each yeast cell displays up to 10⁵ copies of fusion protein [Boder & Wittrup 2000], but individual expression levels may differ based on the stability and solubility of the displayed molecule.

Figure 39. The yeast surface display platform. (A) Schematic representation of yeast surface display plasmid construct. (B) Displayed protein on the yeast cell surface. Mutant protein is displayed on the yeast cell surface as a fusion to the Aga2p cell wall protein. The HA and c-myc epitope tags can be used for immunofluorescent labelling and detection [Cherf & Cochran 2015].

Target protein accessibility can be increased by increasing the length of the anchor protein [Sato et al. 2002] or by adjusting the length of the spacer between the target and anchor proteins [Breinig & Schmitt 2002, Washida et al. 2001]. The choice of promoter and secretion signals are also important factors affecting the amount of displayed proteins [Kajiwara et al. 2020].

The yeast strain *Pichia pastoris*, can be considered for experiments in which displaying of glycoproteins is needed. Posttranslational modifications in *S. cerevisiae* can lead to protein hyperglycosylation, which can interfere with overall protein accessibility on the surface [Ryckaert et al. 2005]. Therefore, less elaborate hyperglycosylation in wild type *Pichia pastoris* strains make this yeast a better choice for surface display of glycoproteins [Jacobs et al. 2008].

Adapter-mediated yeast cell surface display system has been developed. Such display system consists of two modules, a display vector and a helper vector, and is capable of displaying proteins of interest through protein-protein interactions [Ito et al. 2009, Wang et al. 2010]. In such mechanism, target protein is fused to an adapter protein (helper vector) and expressed as soluble fraction into the medium. Second adapter protein (display vector) is displayed on the yeast cell surface as the scaffold connected to anchor protein. As a result, secreted protein of interest is displayed on yeast cell surface via interactions of two small adapters.

Anchor protein can fuse with either N- or C – terminus of the target protein. The choice of the fusion terminus and anchor protein depends on the engineered protein, but the decision should be well considered, because the site of the fusion may significantly impact whether the target protein retains its function when displayed [Tanaka et al. 2012]. Generally, the terminus farther from the functional site is the one tethered to the fusion protein [Tanaka et al. 2012]. While single C- or N-terminal fusions represent classical approach for construction of fusion proteins, not long ago, Cochran and colleagues introduced simplified yeast display strategy in which both, N- and C-termini of Aga2p, were utilized to display two heterologous proteins as part of one fusion protein [Lim et al. 2017].

Genetically, the Aga2p subunit is encoded on a plasmid and its expression is under the control of a galactose-inducible promotor (GAL1). On the other hand, Aga1p subunit is encoded within the yeast genome, and it is also controlled by a GAL1 promotor sequence. The assembly of Aga1p and Aga2p is ensured by the formation of two disulfide bonds. Commonly used yeast surface display construct includes gene for Aga2p, sequence of target protein and two epitope tags: a nine amino acid hemagglutinin (HA) tag between Aga2p and the N-terminus of the target protein, and ten amino acid C-terminal c-myc tag [Boder & Wittrup 1997] (Figure 39A). Two epitope tags allow quantification of fusion protein independent of

antigen, and so normalization of protein properties to expression level by flow cytometry. Although, epitope tags detection does not provide information on the fold or function of the target protein. Therefore, to investigate these characteristics, there is a need to use a specific antibody or ligand that recognize native fold of the displayed protein.

As mentioned earlier, engineering of proteins using yeast surface display has become a valuable mean to improve affinity, reaction kinetics, increase stability or alter the substrate specificity of the protein [Cherf & Cochran 2015, Linciano et al. 2019]. YSD thus represents an effective tool for protein and cellular manipulation and has facilitated countless applications in research, biotechnology, medicine, and industry.

Specific binding proteins engineering

Well-characterized specific binding proteins are essential instruments in therapeutic and diagnostic applications as well as in research. Traditionally, these have been antibodies, but the last decade non-antibody alternative scaffolds have caught attention [Könning & Kolmar 2018].

Therapeutic antibodies have become the predominant class of new drugs and requirements for their commercial production are increasing constantly [Lu et al. 2020]. Along with full-length antibodies, the market of antigen-binding fragments (Fabs), single chain variable fragments (scFv) and heavy chain-only antibodies (nanobodies) has been growing steadily too (Figure 40). For the moment, almost all approved commercial antibodies are produced in mammalian hosts, what is usually time and money consuming [Bradbury & Plückthun 2015]. Moreover, they often show poor specificity or fail to recognize their targets [Bordeaux et al. 2010]. As the demand for antibodies expands, there is a growing need for development of more efficient methods producing antibodies with improved quality and specificity. For this purpose, various recombinant antibody display platforms have been developed [Harel Inbar & Benhar 2012]. The most widely adopted among them is yeast display. Many full-length antibodies and antibody fragments have successfully been tailored using YSD to improve affinity [Wang et al. 2016], stability or pH-sensitivity [Könning et al. 2016, Schröter et al. 2018]. The majority of examples of antibody display on yeast have been scFvs [Boder et al. 2012, Lee & Jeong 2015], but full-length immunoglobulin [Rakestraw et al.

2011], Fab fragments [Blaise et al. 2004, Mei et al. 2019] and nanobodies [Dong et al. 2010] have been successfully displayed in yeast, too. The classical YSD technique described by Boder and Wittrup [Boder & Wittrup 1997] has been modifying throughout the years to comply with the requirements needed for the antibody or antibody fragment engineering [Boder et al. 2012, Cherf & Cochran 2015, Lee & Jeong 2015].

Figure 40. Example of antibodies and antibody fragments [Doshi et al. 2014].

Nanobodies, derived from camelid or shark heavy chain antibodies, are small (15 kDa) antibody fragments binding to their target antigens through a single variable domain, termed VHH [Hamers-Casterman et al. 1993]. Single-domain nature of the VHH, good resistance against temperature and chemicals, and its easy surface immobilization borrow nanobodies competitive advantages over scFvs or any other antigen-binding fragment derived from conventional antibodies [Nguyen et al. 2001]. Moreover, unlike the Fabs, nanobodies production is more straightforward thanks to their expression in bacteria or yeast as the product of a single gene [Ryckaert et al. 2010]. Nanobodies have been shown to bind deep protein cavities including enzyme active-sites [Lauwereys et al. 1998] and G-protein binding cavities on G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) [Manglik et al. 2017, Ring et al. 2013], therefore, they have emerged as important research tools especially in GPRs. Recently, new technique for generation of synthetic recombinant nanobody based on somatic hypermutation inside engineered yeast was introduced. Nearly all nanobodies available today

have been obtained by animal immunisation, which is a constriction for wider usage of this technology. Therefore, fully in vitro platform for rapid nanobody discovery, independent of animal immunization, based on yeast surface display has been developed lately [McMahon et al. 2018]. In Autonomous Hypermutation yeast surface Display (AHEAD), antibody fragments are encoded on an error-prone orthogonal DNA replication system, resulting in *S. cerevisiae* populations that continuously mutate surface-displayed antibody repertoires. Simple cycles of yeast culturing and enrichment for antigen binding drive the evolution of high-affinity antibody clones in a process that takes as little as 2 weeks [Wellner et al. 2020]. Uchanski and colleagues [Uchański et al. 2019] presented an improved yeast display system in which nanobodies were fused instead of C-terminus of Aga2p to the N-terminus, leaving complementary-determining region fully exposed to antigen. Moreover, the display level of a cloned nanobody on the surface of an individual yeast cell could be monitored through a covalent fluorophore that was attached in a single enzymatic step to an orthogonal acyl carrier protein [ACP].

As indicated previously, the generation of antibody Fab immune libraries for YSD is more complicated when comparing to nanobodies, due to the necessity of correct pairing of different heavy and light chains in haploid yeast cells. In the recent past, a simplified procedure for the creating of such libraries based on Golden Gate Cloning was described [Rosowski et al. 2018]. By application of this technology, combinatorial libraries could be easily constructed in just one single step.

Bispecific [bsAb) antibodies are new next generation antibody conjugates, that can simultaneously target two distinct antigens on different cells [Carter & Lazar 2018]. An attractive bsAb feature is their potential for novel functionalities — that is, activities that cannot be mediated by conventional monoclonal antibodies. Generation of bispecific molecules is problematic since the antigen-binding sites are built by the variable domains of the light and heavy chain [VL, VH]. A bispecific antibody requires two different heavy chains, and two different light chains. To direct correct assembly of heavy and light chains, is one of the challenges of generating bispecific antibodies, and various strategies have been development and established over the past two decades to solve this problem [Brinkmann & Kontermann 2017]. Krah and colleagues [Krah et al. 2017] described a generic approach for

the generation of fully human IgG-like bsAbs. They combined heavy chain repertoires from immunized transgenic rats with either a randomly chosen common light chain or a light chain of an existing therapeutic antibody and screened for binders by yeast surface display. Another group reported the isolation of the first biparatopic [antibody targeting two epitops on the same molecule) cLC antibody from immunized chickens utilizing yeast surface display in combination with yeast biopanning and FACS [Bogen et al. 2021].

High-throughput synthetic biology technology that combines a CRISPR/Cas9 based trackable editing methodology and fluorescent-activated cell sorting (FACS) of yeast-displayed libraries [multiplex navigation of antibody structure (MINAS)], was used for multiplex evolution of antibody fragment [Oh et al. 2020].

Although, yeast display offers powerful alternatives to traditional immunization-based antibody discovery, selected candidates usually need to be solubilized for further characterization. This usually slows the validation of engineered proteins and limits the number of protein variants evaluated. To overcome this limitation, Van Deventer and colleagues presented a yeast-based approach for switchable display/secretion system [Van Deventer et al. 2015]. They used amber stop codon suppression to enable the display of an antibody-like protein on the yeast surface only when the media was supplemented with a noncanonical amino acid. The 'switch' between display and secretion was therefore mediated entirely by medium supplementation with a small molecule. Another approach for simultaneous cell surface display and soluble secretion, based on inefficient ribosomal skipping, was developed by Rao and colleagues [Cruz-Teran et al. 2017, 2020].

In addition to antibodies, alternative non-antibody scaffold proteins have emerged as a promising class of biomolecules. These affinity reagents are based on non-antibody structures and they provide several advantages, such as improved tissue penetration, smaller size, superior stability, and cost-efficient production [Koide et al. 2012]. Published alternative scaffold proteins and enzymes which have been engineered using yeast surface display encompass Fn3 domain of fibronectin, human kringle domains, designed ankyrin repeated proteins [DARPin], cystine-knot miniproteins, Sso7d, VHH domains, β -lactamase or tobacco Etch Virus protease [Könning & Kolmar 2018].

DARPin are binders of high affinity and specificity with a scaffold derived from natural ankyrin proteins. As the name implies, they consist of smaller repeat units, typically 3-6 ankyrin repeats and possess a molecular weight in the range of 14–17 kDa [Koenning & Schaefer, 2021]. YSD was used to map epidermal growth factor receptor epitops for DARPins [Boersma et al. 2011]. More recently, ribosome display followed by YSD selections was used to select a DARPin with strong fluorescence activation of malachite green dyes [Schutz 2016].

Membrane proteins

There is a major interest in evolving antibodies that specifically target membrane proteins, but such selection is challenging. Most antibody engineering platforms require soluble target antigen which is often problematic for membrane proteins. This problem can be overcome either by using cell lysate containing target membrane proteins or by yeast biopanning [Tillotson et al. 2013]. In a recent study, an affinity based magnetization of target-displaying cells, mediated by interactions between iron oxide nanoparticles and a coexpressed iron oxide binding protein was employed to select library members binding to membrane proteins [Bacon et al. 2019].

Different situation is when membrane proteins are subjects of directed evolution. The G-protein coupled receptor (GPCR), also known as seven-transmembrane domain receptors are known cell surface drug binders. Due to their key role in pathophysiology, GPCRs remain an important target for basic research and applied biotechnological research. Nevertheless, working with GPCRs is problematic. The major limitations in GPCRs investigation are low insufficient production yields and their instability in solution [Milic & Veprintsev 2015], thus the research and development focus on the requirement to obtain enough functional protein preferably stable in solution. The group of Plückthun [Schütz et al. 2016] introduced a widely applicable method employing directed evolution of GPCRs in yeast that allows fast and efficient generation of receptor variants with increased production levels in eukaryotic hosts. The evolved variants showed up to a 26-fold increase of functional production in insect cells compared to the wild-type receptors and exhibited improved biophysical properties. Recently, GPCR/YSD complex was used as a biosensor for SARS-CoV-2 detection [Maneira et al. 2021].

Biotechnology and industry

While nature has provided abundance of functionally diverse enzymes, majority of them have evolved to function within a narrow range of physiological environment. Therefore, naturally occurring enzymes usually don't function properly under industrial conditions. To address this problem, researchers have used cell surface display for engineering and selecting enzymes more suitable for industrial processing [Cherry & Fidantsef 2003, Porter et al. 2016].

Enzymes displayed on the cell surface enable the bioconversion of high-molecular-weight substrates that cannot enter cells. Displaying enzyme on the yeast overcomes limitations associated with enzyme purification and substrate transport. Further, in the display system, various types of enzymes can be allocated in close proximity, so that their synergism is greater than when they exist individually [Inokuma et al. 2018]. Up till now, YSD implementation has improved cellular functions in a wide range of applications such as biocatalysis [bioremediation and biofuel production), bioadsorption [recovery of rare metal ions) and biosensors development [Park 2020, Wu et al. 2008].

Biocatalyst generally refers to free or immobilized enzymes, which could be used to catalyze certain reaction with high efficiency under normal temperature and pressure. Coupling cell surface display with directed evolution has emerged as a powerful approach for engineering of biocatalysts. Various enzymes have been presented on the surfaces of cells with favourable catalytic activity and stability [Han et al. 2018].

Basic form of YSD employ presentation of a single protein with the purpose of improving enzyme's stability, activity or substrate specificity [Smith et al. 2015]. Another approach to improve catalytic activity on the yeast cell surface is to increase the number of active enzymes immobilized in the cell wall, in other words, improvement of yeast cell surface efficiency. This includes already mentioned approaches, such as choosing proper anchor protein and fusion terminus [Tanaka et al. 2012], but also engineering of signal sequences that are able to enhance protein secretion, the overexpression of proteins involved in cell-surface display or deletion of the genes of the host cell [Tanaka & Kondo 2015]. Multistep and synergistic reactions can be accomplished by co-displaying multienzymes. A sequential enzyme system includes several different enzymes, displayed on the cell surface situated next

to each other. They catalyze a cascade reaction, i.e., the product of the first enzymatic reaction is the substrate for another or several subsequent reactions.

Yeast cell surface display of enzymes has been used for detection or degradation of pollutants [a process known as bioremediation]. Recently, a whole-cell biocatalyst based on displaying a novel PET-hydrolyzing enzyme PETase was developed [Chen et al. 2020]. Authors found that PETase could be functionally displayed on the surface of yeast cell and the turnover rate of the PETase-displaying yeast towards highly crystallized PET increased about 36-fold compared to soluble PETase. Moreover, the whole cell biocatalyst showed stable turnover rate after repeated use and under some chemical/solvent conditions and had ability to degrade different commercial highly crystallized PET bottles. Anchor protein and induction time had great impacts on the enzymatic activity of displayed PETase. Surface-engineered yeast strain was used also for the bioadsorption and bioremediation of environmental mercury or cadmium contaminants [Wei et al. 2016, 2018].

Recombinant *S. cerevisiae* strains displaying the heterologous hydrolytic enzymes on their surface are favourable biocatalysts for the direct conversion of various biomass substrates to ethanol. Several groups have produced ethanol from starchy materials using amylase, cellulase- and hemicellulase-displaying yeast strains [Inokuma et al. 2018]. Lipase enzymes are also commonly applied in YSD systems because they are used in wide range of industries and because the display of lipase is an attractive approach for creating a whole cell biocatalyst [Kuroda & Ueda 2013]. Direct display of lipases on *Pichia pastoris* has resulted in the generation of safe, whole-cell biocatalyst capable of efficiently enriching polyunsaturated fatty acids from fish oil with high selectivity and reducing the energy costs [Pan et al. 2012].

Recent advance in this field includes the engineering of highly specific, modular protein scaffolds. To address the challenges of relative ratio and relative position among individual enzymes and substrate channelling in multienzyme biocatalysis, Yang and colleagues developed a method for multienzyme complexes (MECs) assembled on *Yarrowia lipolytica* yeast based on simultaneous surface display of a synthetic multiple cohesins backbone [scaffoldin] and extracellular secretion of dockerin-fusions of individual enzymes. This adopted technology provided an efficient platform for creating tailored multienzymes for

advanced cascade biosynthesis [Yang et al. 2018]. A complex multiple-component assembly system based on synthetic scaffolding displaying cellulosomes on the *S. cerevisiae* cell surface was constructed through disulfide bonds [Tang et al. 2018]. The newly designed cellulosomes enabled yeast to directly ferment cellulose into ethanol.

YSD was successfully used also as a biosensor. Yeast cell surfaces displaying fluorescent proteins have been applied in optical biosensors, and enzyme surface displaying yeast cells were applied to electrochemical and optical biosensors [Park 2020].

As can be seen, YSD platform has a great potential not only in the field of biotechnology and medicine, but also in the industry. Many YSD tailored antibodies, antibody fragments and alternative binding proteins are clinically approved or have reached late state clinical trials. Many others are under development. YSD technology has found its role also in the field of industry. With the expanding global commercial production, there is an emergent search not only for new low-cost production processes, but also for the method to safely remove generated materials, by-products and waste. YSD method offers an alternative option how to address this demand.

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